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MAPPING AND CATEGORISING OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

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ACRONYMS

BE	Belgium
BG	Bulgaria
DE	Germany
DECC	Department of Energy and Climate Change (UK)
EE	Estonia
EU	European Union
GR	Greece
IT	Italy
LEAP	Long-range Energy Alternatives Planning system
SMEs	Small-Medium sized Enterprises
UK	United Kingdom

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the cross-analysis of the cross-cutting social, economic, cultural, educational and institutional barriers to the implementation of energy efficiency in the building and transport sectors for all eight HERON partner countries. The cross-cutting barriers relate to barriers that affect both the transport and building sectors, and this report seeks to build on the individual barriers within the building and transport sectors that were identified in D.2.1 'Mapping social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in buildings and transport'. The report is based on the eight individual national reports from the HERON partner countries, included in Annexes, and sought to clarify and integrate the cross-cutting barriers identified within these individual reports.

This report first outlines the common social, cultural, educational, economic and institutional cross-cutting barriers, followed by an assessment of the level of potential impact of the cross-cutting barriers. The final section presents a review of the partner countries in terms of whether or not cross-sector, or sector-specific only, policy instruments are currently in place to tackle the cross-cutting barriers.

CHAPTER 1: MAPPING CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

The following cross-cutting barriers across the building and transport sectors are based on the national reports from the eight partner countries as part of D.2.2 (Annexes 1 to 8), as well as the overall D2.1 report (Gupta et al., 2015). In the individual national reports, there are cases of similar barriers being described slightly differently. In order to provide cohesive and consistent reporting within this overall report, common language is used to describe these, and as such the names of the barriers outlined in this report may differ from those used in the individual national reports. In addition, some of the barriers listed in the individual national reports covered similar ground to more than one of the 'standardised' barriers, and have been split accordingly in some cases. Similarly, there were also cases of more than one barrier listed in the individual national reports, covering similar ground to one of the 'standardised' barriers within this report, and report D.2.1, and as such have been grouped (or clustered) accordingly.

In terms of the cross-sectoral barriers, it needs to be stressed that the two sectors themselves have different fundamental characteristics, making a one-to-one translation of single barriers difficult, and instead clusters of barriers can be found instead. In addition, the barriers listed in this report are based on a literature review, and some barriers may not have been listed either because there is no evidence available for the respective barrier, in one or both of the sectors (building and transport), or the principles by which the barrier influences the efficiency of the two sectors are quite different. An example from Germany highlights this; age has a clear influence on private energy efficiency investments in the buildings sector (i.e. decreasing willingness to invest in energy efficiency measures), while the relationship between age and investments in vehicles is more mixed; the majority of new vehicles which tend to be more energy efficient are owned by people older than 50 years and used (typically less energy efficient) vehicles are more common among younger people, but younger people tend to own vehicles with smaller engine size (KBA, 2011).

Similar to D.2.1, the number of 'standardised' barriers per individual partner countries is varied (Figure 1). This is considered to be due to the lack of relevant literature and it is not necessarily a direct result of the actual number of barriers encountered in the country. Across the partner countries, the types of barrier present seem fairly evenly split; with a total of 19 'standardised' barriers, of which five are social/cultural, three are educational, five are economic barriers and six are institutional barriers. Therefore, there appears to be a fairly even spread of types of cross-cutting barriers across the partner countries in total; with social/cultural and economic barriers appearing to be the most common cross-cutting barriers in most of the partner countries.

Figure 1 Types of cross-cutting barriers across all partner countries. Note:- UK = United Kingdom; GR = Greece; SB = Serbia; EE = Estonia; IT = Italy; DE = Germany; BE = Belgium; BG = Bulgaria

1.1 SOCIAL, CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

As shown in Table 1 and Figure 2, the most common social, cultural and educational cross-cutting barriers indicated by the HERON partner countries are related to ***‘undervaluing energy efficiency’*** (seven nations); ***‘social group interactions and status considerations’*** (six nations); ***‘lack of awareness on savings potential’*** (six nations); and ***‘lack of access to trusted information and knowledge’*** (six nations). *‘Undervaluing energy efficiency’* relates to limited environmental concern, buyer attitudes and the low prioritisation of energy efficiency in terms of consumer purchases, whether it be a new vehicle, wall insulation or a new washing machine. Furthermore, the undervaluing of energy efficiency effects both domestic and commercial consumers in the building and transport sectors; as highlighted in research from the UK and Germany, people prefer amenities such as new kitchens, bathrooms and general repairs and often do not consider energy efficient refurbishments as the social gains are not as obvious (Bell & Lowe, 2000; Hacke & Lohmann, 2006), whilst in private companies, energy efficiency improvements may not be seen as strategic for a company, as energy bills are only a small proportion of overall business costs (DECC, 2012). In addition, research from most of the partner countries that indicate this as a barrier, highlight the fact that energy efficiency is a low priority for the consumer, with comfort, ease-of-use, time-saving features, safety and price all being seen as higher priorities.

In addition, *‘undervaluing energy efficiency’* is also closely linked to the barriers of *‘lack of awareness on savings potential’*, *‘lack of access to trusted information and knowledge’* and *‘social group interactions and status considerations’*, amongst many others. As research from Greece

indicates, end-users of both the building and transport sectors often do not understand, or are aware of, the benefits that energy efficient technologies and practices can bring to their daily life (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012; Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011; ECOWILL project, 2010; Ad Personam project, 2009; 2010) and fear for such technologies, alongside restricted financial incentives, reinforce this barrier (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). Research from the UK highlights the fact that '*lack of awareness on savings potential*' can be encountered even among consumers, architects, engineers, builders, contractors, installers and building operators (NERA Economic Consulting, 2007) and is linked to another barrier that was identified across many partner countries, that of '*lack of trained and skilled professionals*'; in terms of builders, contractors and manufacturers (building sector) as well as HGV/commercial drivers (transport sector). Within Germany, the distinction between a lack of awareness of consumed energy and CO₂ emissions is discussed separately to the lack of awareness of other co-benefits of energy efficient technologies and practices, such as comfort gains, wider sustainability benefits and quality of life. The idea of 'bounded rationality' in terms of the misperception of the building condition is linked to the lack of awareness in terms of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions, with a study from Germany indicating that 60% of respondents felt that their dwelling were at a good standard in terms of energy efficiency (Stieß et al., 2010). However, public perception of a 'good' standard often differs from political objectives and BAT standards (e.g. triple-glazing instead of double-glazing) (Krémer et al., 2005). In relation to the transport sector, this barrier is an issue as the awareness of vehicle emissions appears to be decreasing (Aral, 2011). In terms of the awareness of other co-benefits, the benefits differ between the transport and building sector (in the buildings sector, the benefits mainly apply to the individual, whilst in the transport sector the main benefits are from a societal perspective such as reduction in poor air quality, noise pollution etc.), but are generally due to a lack of information and the way in which the costs and benefits are appraised by individuals (Hüging et al., 2014).

'*Social group interactions and status considerations*', relate to the fact that the behaviour of consumers is not always the result of conscious and motivated action, and everyday energy-related behaviours are strongly shaped and influenced at the micro-level, as highlighted in research from Serbia (Stadtmüller H. 2014); in other words, lifestyle has an influence on purchase decisions and common practice (Mrkajic V. et al. 2015) and social 'norms' relating to energy reduction within an individual's social network, and wider community, influence their behaviours, practices and attitudes towards energy efficiency (Lynn et al., 2014). Although applicable to both the building and transport sectors, a barrier such as *status considerations* appear to be particularly relevant in terms of private vehicle purchasing as highlighted in research from Greece, Germany, Serbia and the UK amongst many of the other partner countries, which indicates that for many people, owning and driving a private car represents a status symbol for good lifestyle, comfort and freedom and these, in turn, affect the prioritisation of energy efficiency within purchasing decisions (CRISP, 2012).

Table 1 Cross-cutting social, cultural and educational barriers across buildings and transport

Types of barriers		BE	BG	DE	EE	GR	IT	SB	UK
Social	Social group interactions and status considerations	x			x	x	x	x	X
	Inertia							x	X
Cultural	Undervaluing energy efficiency (low priority of energy efficiency; lack of environmental consciousness/interest)	x		x	x	x	x	x	x
	Customs, habits and relevant behavioural aspects	x			x	x		x	x
	Mistrust/negative perception of new technologies					x		x	x
Educational	Lack of awareness on savings potential (energy and non-energy related benefits)			x	x	x	x	x	x
	Lack of access to trusted information and knowledge	x	x		x	x		x	x
	Lack of expertise (skills & training) and highly qualified specialists				x	x			

Figure 2 Main social, cultural and educational barriers across all partner countries

1.2 ECONOMIC CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

As shown in Table 2 and Figure 3, the most common economic cross-cutting barriers indicated by the HERON partner countries are related to **'lack of financial incentive / access to finance'** (seven nations); and **'high capital costs'** (six nations). Lack of funds or access to finance can relate to the inability to find a loan for a system or renovation because the funding agent will not back the investment (reluctance to contract a loan). Some people are also unable to get access to finance because of their financial history. This not only is a problem for individuals but can also be a problem for businesses such as small-medium sized hotels in Greece; due to poor credit ratings, smaller hotels face more costly loans than hotel chains. This barrier highlights the need for financial incentives for energy efficiency technologies in the due to high upfront (capital) costs of energy efficient technologies in most of the partner countries, and the low purchasing power of citizens in some of the partner countries, such as Serbia. Whilst it is a cross-cutting barrier across both the building and transport sector, in countries such as Belgium and Germany, it appears to be a barrier in the transport sector in particular; with a lack of financial resources for public transport in Germany, and the authorities in Belgium favouring subsidies and tax investment credits for the building sector rather than for the transport sector.

'High capital costs' are a cross-cutting barrier in Bulgaria, Germany, Italy, Serbia and the UK. Research from the UK suggests that cost is a primary barrier to the adoption of energy efficiency measures and practices (Pelenur & Cruickshank, 2012a and 2012b; UK-GBC, 2008), particularly in

terms of low carbon microgeneration and heating technologies (Allen et al., 2008; Claudy et al., 2010; Scarpa & Willis, 2010; Wee et al., 2012). In Germany, surveys (BMUB and UBA, 2015) have shown that 87% of the respondents were of the opinion that electric vehicles were too expensive. As shown in the example of the UK, the barrier of ‘high capital costs’ is closely linked to ‘payback expectations / investment horizons’ in both the building and transport sectors (Lane & Potter, 2007) as well as the education barrier of ‘lack of awareness of savings potential’ (Pelenur & Cruickshank, 2012b). Life-costs are seen as an important criteria in terms of vehicle purchasing decisions (Bozem et al., 2013), with a survey from Germany indicating that if the cost of alternatively fuelled vehicles were comparable to those of diesel and gasoline vehicles, 80% of respondents would consider switching to a vehicle running on alternative fuels. Finally in some countries, such as Italy, Greece and Serbia, the economic stagnation or strain has created a condition where credit is difficult to access, which therefore further limits the potential of energy efficiency investments, whether it be in the building or transport sector.

Table 2 Cross-cutting economic barriers across buildings and transport

Barrier	BE	BG	DE	EE	GR	IT	SB	UK
Lack of Financial Incentive / access to finance	x	x	x		x	x	x	x
High capital costs		x	x			x	x	x
Payback expectations / Investment horizons			x		x			x
Lack of / uncertainty of investment (public & private)			x	x				x
Financial crisis / Economic stagnation					x	x	x	

Figure 3 Main economic cross-cutting barriers across the partner countries

1.3 INSTITUTIONAL CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

As shown in Table 3 and Figure 4, the most common institutional cross-cutting barriers indicated by the HERON partner countries are related to **'lack of / complex legislative procedures and regulatory provision'** (five nations); **'non-integrated and conflicting policies and targets'** (four nations); and **'inadequate implementation network / governance framework'** (four nations). The most common institutional barrier, **'lack of / complex legislative procedures and regulatory provision'**, is linked to the barriers of **'non-integrated and conflicting policies and targets'** and **'inadequate implementation network / governance framework'**. In Greece, this barrier is particularly related to end-users such as hotels, which do not adopt energy efficient technologies or practices due to the lack of any effective national legislative policies in the tourism sector to supplement the existing energy efficiency policy instruments that are within the UNFCCC framework and the Kyoto Protocol (Pieri et al., 2015). Furthermore, in the transport sector in Greece, the lack of regulatory and legislative procedures adds further complexity to the barriers of **'non-integration and conflicting policies and targets'** in relation to transportation means and the urban/spatial development strategies that have been developed separately (Pitsiava-Latinopoulou M. et al., 2014; Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006). In the UK, the lack of regulatory provision within the building sector is closely linked with the lack of knowledge and skills within the construction industry in relation to the as-built performance of energy efficient measures (Boardman, 2007). In the transport sector, a lack of clarity in terms of standards and regulations is a barrier to the uptake and development of a cohesive energy efficient transport sector. The standardization of technical specifications such as cables and plugs for recharging was identified widely as an important issue by industry interviewees in a research study (Steinhilber et al., 2013) as currently there is a disconnect between infrastructure installers and vehicle manufacturers (Keith et al., 2013). Furthermore, there is no clear regulation as to where public EV charging spots may be installed and there are unclear regulations regarding parking on spaces equipped with a charging spot (Steinhilber et al., 2013).

Cited by four partner countries, the barrier of **'inadequate implementation network / governance framework'** appeared to be one of the most complex and relates to a variety of specific barriers within the partner countries; including lack of support, capacity, co-ordination and clarity across different administrative levels. Furthermore, in the majority of partner countries that cite this as a barrier, the barrier of **'inadequate planning framework and infrastructure'** is closely interlinked. In Estonia, the barrier related to the fact that work within the building and transport sectors are split between many different administrative levels and/or departments. This in itself has led to a lack of integrated governance in general, making it hard to find common understanding of principal issues. Furthermore, this barrier has led to a lack of co-operation and understanding between local municipalities in Estonia, which, in turn, has led to a lack of integrated transport and land-use planning framework; another institutional barrier highlighted by other partner countries. Within Greece, the performance of the implementation framework is seen as a barrier in both transport and building sectors, due either to the absence of necessary actions/entities or due to overlapping responsibilities, which, in turn, do not provide end-users with the assistance they require. Greece highlights an example within the transport sector where more than one authority is responsible for the planning of the system of public transportation in the big urban centres, and does not enable

integrated urban planning, particularly in terms of energy efficient transport infrastructure (Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006). Ineffective urban planning causes problems to mass-transportation system, since it fails to displace the car dominance and diminish congestion – related problems (Saliara K., 2014; Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006), particularly through a lack of public bus networks; traffic and congestion due to the lack of parking control and the traffic management (Ministry of T&C, 2006); and the charging infrastructure for electric vehicles, making the consumers hesitating for their purchases (YPEKA, 2012).

Table 3 Cross-cutting institutional barriers across buildings and transport

Barrier	BE	BG	DE	EE	GR	IT	SB	UK
Lack of / complex legislative procedures and regulatory provision			x		x	x	x	x
Non-integrated and conflicting policies and targets	x		x		x	x		
Inadequate implementation network / governance framework				x	x	x	x	
Inadequate planning framework and infrastructure				x	x			x
Limitations of existing technologies and infrastructure								x
Immature status of developing technologies (lack of data / research)								x

Figure 4 Main cross-cutting institutional barriers across all partner countries

1.4 ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF KEY CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

This section provides an assessment of the key cross-cutting barriers in the HERON partner countries in terms of their impact on energy efficiency. The identified barriers are assessed from 'High' to 'Low', with the following criteria taken into consideration:

- The number of different resources that identified the same barrier;
- The number of sub-sectors that were linked with the same barrier;
- The easiness with which the barrier can be confronted;
- The duration of the barrier;
- The number of different policy instruments that were linked with the same type of barrier.

In total, there are 19 cross-cutting barriers outlined across the eight partner countries. Table 4 and Figure 5 outline the level of impact of the cross-cutting barriers (social, cultural, educational, economic and institutional). The impacts of the different types of barrier are mixed, with one social/cultural barrier, two economic barriers and two educational barriers making up the top five most cited, and potentially with the greatest impacts. Within the partner countries, the impacts of the barriers can also vary; in terms of *'undervaluing energy efficiency'*, four partner countries rated it as high impact (Belgium, Germany, Italy and the UK), two medium impact (Estonia and Greece) and one low impact (Serbia). The cultural barrier of *'undervaluing energy efficiency'* and the economic barrier of *'lack of financial incentive / access to finance'* are the barriers most cited by the partner countries. They are also rated high in four of the seven partner countries, in terms of their impact.

Educational barriers such as *'lack of access to trusted information and knowledge'* and *'lack of awareness on savings potential'* are also rated highly in terms of impact, and are cited by the majority of the partner countries. It is therefore clear from these findings that limited information and lack of understanding and experience of both the public and professionals can lead to a series of issues that undermine energy efficiency in both buildings and transport. The institutional barriers of *'non-integrated and conflicting policies and targets'* and *'inadequate implementation network / governance framework'* and the economic barrier of *'lack of / uncertainty of investment (public and private)'*, whilst cited by fewer partner countries, are rated more highly overall than barriers such as *'social group interactions and status considerations'* and *'lack of awareness on savings potential'*, despite these being cited by more partner countries.

Table 4 Assessment of impact of cross-cutting barriers

Barriers		BE	BG	DE	EE	GR	IT	SB	UK
Cul	Undervaluing energy efficiency	High		High	Med	Med	High	Low	High
Eco	Lack of Financial Incentive / access to finance	High	High	High		Low	Med	High	Low
Eco	High capital costs		High	High		Med	Med	High	High
Edu	Lack of access to trusted information and knowledge	Med	Med		Med	High		High	High
Edu	Lack of awareness on savings potential			Med	Med	Low	High	Med	Med
Soc	Social group interactions and status considerations	High			High	Low	High	Low	Low
Inst	Lack of / complex legislative procedures and regulatory provision			High		Med	High	Med	Med
Cul	Customs, habits and relevant behavioural aspects	High			Med	Low		Med	Low
Inst	Inadequate implementation network / governance framework				High	High	High	High	
Inst	Non-integrated and conflicting policies and targets	High		High		Med	High		
Eco	Lack of / uncertainty of investment (public & private)			High	High				High
Eco	Payback expectations / Investment horizons			Med		Med			High
Eco	Financial crisis / Economic stagnation					Med	Med	High	
Cul	Mistrust of new technologies					Med		Med	High
Inst	Inadequate planning framework and infrastructure				High	Med			Med
Soc	Inertia							Med	High
Edu	Lack of expertise (skills & training) and highly qualified specialists				Med	Low			
Inst	Practical limitations of existing technologies and infrastructure								High
Inst	Immature status of developing technologies (lack of data / research)								Med
Notes:-									
1. Med = medium; Cul = cultural; Eco = economic; Edu = educational; Soc = social; Inst = institutional									

Figure 5 Assessment of impact of cross-cutting barriers across all partner countries

1.5 CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS AND POLICY INSTRUMENTS

Whilst the overall energy efficiency policies of the partner countries addressed the need to focus on the building and transport sectors, most of the partner countries did not find evidence of policy instruments that directly addressed the cross-cutting barriers identified, in both the building and transport sector. The main exceptions were Estonia, Belgium and the UK. Estonia outlined the financial support scheme of Foundation KredEx, which is an authority that provides financial support for electric vehicles as well as building related energy efficiency measures for apartment co-operatives and home owners. In Estonia, the high impact barrier of *'lack of expertise (skills and training)'* is also being targeted by concerted efforts to set up new study programmes in universities across the country that directly deal with the energy efficiency in both the building and transport sector. In Belgium, there is an informative federal website (energy guzzlers) where information relating to energy efficient appliances and vehicles is available to the Belgian public. The Federal Public Service (FPS) Health, Food chain Safety and Environment; Directorate-general for Environment (DG5) - Climate Change Section, department of Product Management and Chemicals and the thematic service "climate change" developed the website and maintain it. However, it is worth noting that the real reason for the existence of the website is not so much the existence of a deliberate cross-cutting energy efficiency policy instrument, but due to the fact that the FPS Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment is responsible for product policies in Belgium. In the UK, energy labelling legislation is applicable in both the building and transport sector, and particularly aims at enhancing awareness of energy consumption of building and transport related technologies such as appliances (buildings) and vehicles (transport).

Despite this, in the majority of the other partner countries, there are sector-specific policy instruments that address the cross-cutting barriers within the building or transport sector, independently. Table 5 outlines the partner countries that have policy instruments in place, in relation to the cross-cutting barriers. The overall D.2.1 report, as well as the individual national D.2.2 reports, provides further details of the individual policy instruments. Examples of the types of policy instruments in place to target the highest ranking cross-cutting barrier of *'undervaluing energy efficiency'* include regulatory (e.g. The Green Deal in the UK), dissemination and awareness (e.g. energy checks and consultations for SMEs in Germany), and economic (e.g. National procurement plan for Green Procurement in public administrations in Italy). Of the partner countries that do not have policy instruments that cover the same cross-cutting barrier in both the building and transport sector, there are more examples of partner countries having policy instruments that target the barrier in the building sector only, than targeting the barrier in the transport sector only. This highlights the need for either further review of the policy instruments in the transport sector, or policy instruments that target the transport sector need to be increased.

In some partner countries, such as Estonia and Greece, a majority of the policy instruments that target the identified cross-cutting barriers are not yet in place; such as in Greece, the Draft Law on the Directive 2012/27/EC is expected to temper the impacts of the barrier *'lack of expertise (skills and training)'*, but is not, as yet, passed into legislation. In Estonia, a key aspect to the barrier of *'inadequate implementation network / governance framework'* is the lack of capacity which is linked

to administrative fragmentation and lack of integrated governance (national to local) in terms of the implementation of policies in the country. To tackle this barrier, the Estonian National Government is currently working out national planning guidance; to increase the capacity of the local governmental authorities to tackle issues related to energy efficiency, sustainable mobility and planning. In other countries, such as the UK, policies addressing both the building and transport sectors are undergoing evaluation, with some previously key policy instruments such as the Green Deal being scrapped due to its underperformance in terms of expected uptake and savings. As such, barriers that were being targeted by policy instruments, particularly in the building sector, are currently not covered; which in turn, could lead to the impacts of cited barriers being higher, and/or other barriers coming more to the fore.

Table 5 Cross-cutting barriers and relevant policy instruments in the building and transport sectors

Barriers	BE		BG		DE		EE		GR		IT		SB		UK		
	B	T	B	T	B	T	B	T	B	T	B	T	B	T	B	T	
Undervaluing energy efficiency (<i>cultural</i>)	-	-			x	x	x	x	-	-	-	x	x	x	x	x	x
Lack of Financial Incentive / access to finance (<i>economic</i>)	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	-	x	x	x	-	x	x	
High capital costs (<i>economic</i>)			x	-	-	x			x	x	x	x	-	-	x	x	
Lack of access to trusted information and knowledge (<i>educational</i>)	-	-	x	x			x	-	x	-			x	x	x	x	
Lack of awareness on savings potential (<i>educational</i>)					-	-	x	x	-	x	-	-	x	x	x	x	
Social group interactions and status considerations (<i>social</i>)	-	-					-	-	-	-	x	x	x	x	-	x	
Lack of / complex legislative procedures and regulatory provision (<i>institutional</i>)					-	-			-	-	x	x	-	-	x	x	
Customs, habits and relevant behavioural aspects (<i>cultural</i>)	-	-					x	x	-	x			-	x	x	x	
Inadequate implementation network / governance framework (<i>institutional</i>)							x	x	-	-	x	x	x	-			
Non-integrated and conflicting policies and targets (<i>institutional</i>)	-	-			-	-			-	-	x	x					
Lack of / uncertainty of investment (public & private) (<i>economic</i>)					x	-	-	x							x	x	
Payback expectations / Investment horizons (<i>economic</i>)					x	x			x	x					x	x	
Financial crisis / Economic stagnation (<i>economic</i>)									x	-	x	x	-	x			
Mistrust of new technologies (<i>cultural</i>)									-	x			-	-	x	-	
Inadequate planning framework and infrastructure (<i>institutional</i>)							-	x	-	-					x	x	
Inertia (<i>social</i>)													x	x	x	-	
Lack of expertise (skills & training) (<i>educational</i>)							x	x	x	-							
Practical limitations of existing technologies and infrastructure (<i>institutional</i>)															x	x	
Immature status of developing technologies (lack of data / research) (<i>institutional</i>)															x	x	

Notes:-

1. Shaded areas indicate that the barrier is not relevant in the partner country
2. B = Building sector; T = Transport sector; x = policy instrument present; - = no policy instrument present

CHAPTER 2: KEY FINDINGS

This report presented the cross analysis of the social, economic, cultural, institutional and educational cross-cutting barriers to energy efficiency progress in the building and transport sectors for all eight HERON partner countries. Similar to the findings of report D.2.1, the cross-cutting barriers are complex, and often involve clusters of similar barriers, identified previously by the partner countries. Furthermore, as per the report D.2.1, the review of national reports showed that there are discrepancies between the number of barriers identified in each of the partner countries in both the building and the transport sectors. This is considered to be due to the lack of relevant literature and does not absolutely reflect the number of barriers encountered in the country. Instead, this finding is pointing to the fact that research on barriers in energy efficiency in buildings and transport is not equally developed across all partners countries, which could in turn hinder the effective implementation of policies.

- The type of cross-cutting barriers appear to relatively evenly spread, with six institutional, five social/cultural, five economic and three educational key cross-cutting barriers identified.
- The cultural barrier of *'undervaluing energy efficiency'* and the economic barrier of *'lack of financial incentive / access to finance'*, are the most common as they are reported by seven countries:
 - Undervaluing energy efficiency is a complex barrier that is related to aspects such as lack of knowledge, inertia and habit. In both the building and transport sector, this can manifest as a lack of interest and low prioritisation of energy efficiency technologies and practices, subsequently leading to reduced or low uptake. In the building sector, this can relate to consumer purchases of energy efficiency technologies such as wall insulation, renewable technologies, efficient lighting and appliances as well as habitual behaviours and practices that could reduce energy consumption not being undertaken due to the prioritisation of comfort, quality of life etc. In the transport sector, this can also be related to consumer purchases of energy efficient vehicles, where cost and even status are higher priorities to the consumer.
 - The most cited economic barrier, that of *'lack of financial incentive / access to finance'*, is closely related to two other well-cited economic barrier; *'high capital costs'* and *'payback expectations / investment horizons'*. A lack of appropriate financial incentives reduces uptake of energy efficient technologies (both building and transport related), even by end-users who are keen to install/use, but who cannot access the necessary initial funds. In Belgium, Bulgaria, Germany and Serbia, lack of funds or access to finance is also a significant cross-cutting barrier. Lack of funds or access to finance can relate to inability to find a loan for a system or renovation because the funding agent will not back the investment (reluctance to contract a loan). In some countries, such as Italy and Greece, the economic stagnation or strain has created a condition where credit is difficult to access; limiting energy efficiency investments. Economic policy instruments are also

closely linked to socio-cultural aspects due to their consumer focus; one size does not fit all, and a successful economic policy instrument needs to consider what groups (social etc.) require access to finance, and then be implemented in ways suitable and accessible by such groups.

- Educational cross-cutting barriers such as *'lack of access to trusted information and knowledge'* and *'lack of awareness on savings potential'* were also cited by most of the partner countries (six nations each), and rated relatively highly in terms of impact:
 - *'Lack of access to trusted information and knowledge'* was rated high impact by Greece, Serbia and the UK. In the UK, two important Government-based organisations, Energy Saving Trust (EST) and Building Research (BRE) were privatised, which has led to a lack of Government supported organisations that can provide trusted information. Such a barrier can hinder the uptake of energy efficient technologies as consumers are unlikely to invest in or purchase items without the provision of information. A lack of trusted and accurate information can also lead or exacerbate consumer's concerns particularly regarding 'new' technologies; items that they have not had prior experience of, or they do not know of people with prior experience.
 - *'Lack of awareness on savings potential'* was rated high impact by Italy only. The savings potential can relate to both energy consumption and CO2 emissions as well as wider environmental and social benefits such as health, comfort and quality of life. Such an impact not only relates to the consumer but also those involved in the manufacturing/installing of energy efficient technologies, particularly in the building sector where it can be closely linked to another cross-cutting educational barrier; *'lack of trained and skilled professionals'*, as well as the socio-cultural cross-cutting barrier of *'mistrust of technologies'*. In terms of the transport sector, such a barrier hinders uptake of energy efficient vehicles, as well as investment in infrastructure.
- Cross-cutting barriers such as *'high capital costs'* (economic) and *'inadequate implementation network / governance framework'* (institutional) rank highly in terms of their impact. In addition, *'lack of / uncertainty of investment (public & private)'* (economic) is also rated high impact by a higher percentage of the partner countries that cited it as a barrier, than other barriers that were cited by more partner countries.
- Only Estonia outlined existing policy instruments that aim to tackle cross-cutting barriers across both the building and transport sector; all other partner countries mainly have policy instruments that are sector-specific.

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ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 NATIONAL REPORT OF BELGIUM

ANNEX 2 NATIONAL REPORT OF BULGARIA

ANNEX 3 NATIONAL REPORT OF ESTONIA

ANNEX 4 NATIONAL REPORT OF GERMANY

ANNEX 5 NATIONAL REPORT OF GREECE

ANNEX 6 NATIONAL REPORT OF ITALY

ANNEX 7 NATIONAL REPORT OF SERBIA

ANNEX 8 NATIONAL REPORT OF UNITED KINGDOM

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.2.2

MAPPING AND CATEGORISING OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

30 SEPTEMBER 2015

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

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ACRONYMS

NPV	Net Present Value
FPS	Federal Public Service
HFO	Heating Fuel Oil

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Empirical research in Belgium on energy efficiency barriers is very limited, and focused on residential buildings. We are not aware of any empirical research addressing cross-cutting barriers. In fact, energy literature in general tends to treat the buildings sector and transport sector as two entirely different subjects. A similar remark applies to energy efficiency (and climate change) policies in Belgium. Both fields are approached almost entirely separate from each other. The only exception is the “energy guzzlers” website, where consumers may find the most energy efficient (household) appliances and vehicles available on the Belgian market.

CHAPTER 1: MAPPING CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

1.1 SOCIAL, CULTURAL, EDUCATIONAL, ECONOMIC AND INSTITUTIONAL CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS IN BELGIUM

Deliverable 2.2 of work package 2 in the HERON project requires a country-specific description of the interrelationships between (energy efficiency) barriers in the building sector and the transport sector. Building energy services relate to space heating, cooling, ventilation, lighting, cooking, appliances, etc. Transport services refer to passenger and or freight transport (home-work travel, home-school travel, etc.). Those two kinds of services are almost always studied separately in Belgium. This is most certainly the case for “energy efficiency barriers”, for which research in general is already very scarce.

There is no (known) research in Belgium that addresses energy efficiency barriers in both sectors (buildings and transport) at the same time and /or for the same target groups. This chapter is by necessity based on expert knowledge, and not on “hard” empirical evidence specific to Belgium.

1.1.1 Social, cultural and educational barriers

From a theoretical point of view, It is difficult to see how a barrier that “prevents” an individual from buying a heat pump, would influence his or her decision to buy an electric vehicle, except that it is obviously the same individual, in the same place and at the same time, and in the same economic, social, cultural and institutional context. Behavioural barriers belong the individuality or even “personality” of the end-user or consumer. There are no reasons, neither from literature, nor from expert knowledge, to assume that a particular consumer would behave one way in one sector (buildings); and in a completely different way in another sector (transport). To believe otherwise, would be to assume that most people are at heart “sector-schizophrenic”.

In the following sections we attempt to describe a few barriers, previously identified in HERON Deliverable D2.1 as major barriers in the buildings and transport sectors in Belgium, and which may or may not be cross-cutting.

1.1.1.1 Social interactions – credibility & trust

Consumption behaviour, including energy consumption behaviour, is significantly influenced by social networks (relatives, friends, colleagues, ...). When refurbishing their homes, households in Belgium attach great value to the advice given by people they know and trust. The choice of transport means is also greatly influenced by others. It is true however that people move in different circles; and that the behaviour of an individual in one circle does not necessarily match 100% his or her actions in another. It is entirely possible that the people whom Belgians trust in matters of home insulation or heating systems; are entirely different from the ones they rely on for advice when buying a car. Again, we do not have any “hard” empirical evidence to back up this claim.

1.1.1.2 Low priority – other attributes

Whether an individual buys a home, or a building energy service installation (heating system, air-conditioning, lighting system, etc.); or chooses a means of transportation; in all those instances “energy efficiency” is most likely not to be one of the salient characteristics of the energy service. There is also no “market” for energy efficiency, in either sector. One buys “the whole package”, and for both an energy-efficient heating system or an energy-efficient car the efficiency of the technology would most likely be a shrouded attribute in the eyes of the consumer. In both instances, “comfort” or “ease of use”, “time-saving features”, “safety”, etc. would be far more prominent features, together with price.

1.1.1.3 The attitude – action gap

Many individuals who assert to be aware of environmental issues including energy efficiency and climate change, do not (always) reflect these “values” or “attitudes” in their behaviour. Again, there is no reason (known to us) to assume that where for one and the same individual this attitude-action gap would exist in one sector (e.g. buildings); it would not exist in another sector (e.g. transport). However, we do not have empirical evidence (for Belgium) to substantiate this claim. It may very well be that the group that demonstrates an attitude-behaviour gap vis-à-vis building energy services, does not show a similar gap for transport services. We believe this line of thought merits further research.

1.1.1.4 Imperfect information (lack of information)

This section refers to three (3) separate barriers in deliverable D2.1, namely:

- Lack of knowledge about government support (imperfect information):
- Inability to estimate the magnitude of energy use (and related costs) (imperfect information);
- Lack of understanding how much energy (money) can be saved (imperfect information).

Lack of information in the eyes of economists is the perfect example of a pure “market failure”. The markets for building energy services (construction, building installations, appliances) and transport services are quite distinct. There is little reason to assume that by definition a failure in one market would be (directly) linked to a failure in one of the other markets. The Belgian federal government nevertheless decided to tackle the information (market) failure regarding (household) appliances and cars with one and the same instrument, the so-called “energy guzzlers” website. Consumers looking for information on energy efficient appliances, would automatically be drawn to similar information regarding energy efficient vehicles in the Belgian market. It has to be noted however that two Regions (Walloon and Flanders) have jointly developed a different website where consumers can find information on “green vehicles”, although their website focuses on vehicles that emit less CO₂, and consequently pay less attention to energy efficiency as such.

1.1.1.5 Heterogeneity across end-users

Consumers belong to different categories, where members within the same category show similar energy saving behaviours; but different from the energy saving behaviours of the members in other

categories. The group of end-users who are willing to take the risk of adopting a new, and likely more expensive, energy-efficient technology for building energy services (for instance investing in photovoltaics), may probably show comparable behaviour in the transport sector (e.g. purchasing battery electric vehicles). Likewise, one can imagine that a certain lifestyle that prevents the uptake of a technology in the building sector (e.g. a conservative lifestyle that tries to avoid 'new-fangled things') would also prevent the acceptance of certain technologies in the transport sector. We have no empirical evidence for Belgium to support this assertion. There is circumstantial evidence that for both sectors belonging to a different "lifestyle segment" may have a substantial impact on energy efficient behaviour (see D2.1 country report for Belgium).

1.1.2 Economic barriers

1.1.2.1 Access to capital

In spite of positive net present values (NPV) over the lifetime of energy efficient technologies, both in the building sector and the transport sector, the initial investment or purchase costs are usually (much) higher compared to conventional technologies. Difficulties in raising the necessary funds are seen as an important barrier by Belgian consumers. The barrier is more stringent in the transport sector however, because both federal and regional authorities focus on the energy efficiency of buildings rather than of vehicles. Most if not all policy instruments aimed at alleviating this particular economic barrier (e.g. subsidies, tax investment credits, soft loans) are consequently directed at measures in the building sector. It may also be the case that, given limited budgets, consumers might still opt for energy efficiency measures in buildings first, even after making abstraction of existing financial incentives, but we have no hard empirical evidence for Belgium.

1.1.2.2 Low energy and transport related taxes

Energy prices according to the economic paradigm of "rational choice theory" without any doubt have a significant effect on energy consumption, both in the buildings sector and the transport sector. However, energy and / or carbon taxes on fossil-based fuels (natural gas, heating fuel oil, gasoline and diesel) too not internalize externalities and are therefore too low in Belgium to have a major impact on energy (saving) behaviour. Those taxes are much more a 'financing' policy instrument than a 'regulatory' one. Of course, it would be the case that if the federal authorities were to substantially raise taxes for diesel oil used for transportation, this would or should in principle have little effect on the use of heating fuel oil (HFO) for space heating. Consumers would probably be tempted to use HFO for their vehicles, as some already do, but that is a criminal offence and an entirely different matter.

1.1.3 Institutional barriers

1.1.3.1 Fragmentation of authority - intraregional

Belgium is a deeply divided country. Energy efficiency competences for both buildings and transport sectors are divided between the federal level and the regions, but also within the regions between several government departments. Furthermore, there is seldom a clear delineation

between the competences. The net effect is that a coordinated effort to integrate built-environment and mobility policies is almost non-existent.

Table 1 Cross-cutting barriers across buildings and transport

Types of barriers	Barriers in building sector	Barriers in transport sector	Description (how these barriers affect each sector)
Social	<i>Credibility and trust. Advice from building professionals has to be corroborated by the opinions of relatives, friends, colleagues, etc.</i>	<i>The group an individual belongs to has a great influence on the choice of vehicle.</i>	The social network that influences energy efficiency decisions regarding building energy services may largely coincide with the social network that influences mobility choices (or again, they may not).
	<i>Heterogeneity of end-users. Although certain measures save energy in general, they may not always be equally efficient depending on some characteristics of the end-users. For instance, the ideal thermal characteristics of the building and of the heating system may depend on the lifestyles of the inhabitants (e.g. at home all day; or 'almost never at home')</i>	<i>Heterogeneity of end-users. The uptake of a fairly new technology is mostly a matter of the so-called "innovators" or "early adopters".</i>	Those who are willing to take the risk of adopting up a new, non-mature technology, in one sector (buildings), may also be willing to take the same risk in another sector (transport).
Cultural	<i>Low priority of energy efficiency – other attributes of dwellings are deemed more important (e.g. thermal, visual and acoustic comfort)</i>	<i>Low priority of energy efficiency – other attributes of cars are deemed more important (e.g. comfort, safety, speed, driving range)</i>	Energy efficiency in both sectors has low visibility (it is a shrouded attribute). Individuals who do not recognize energy efficiency as a salient characteristic of a building energy service, are less likely to regard

			energy efficiency as a prominent feature of mobility; and vice versa
	<i>Attitude-action gap. Environmentally aware households do not on average consume less energy for building energy services than less environmentally aware households.</i>	<i>Attitude-action gap.. Positive attitudes towards “green vehicles” do not necessarily lead to purchasing energy efficient cars.</i>	There is no empirical evidence (at least not that we are aware of) that would suggest that a similar (positive) attitude towards environmental issues would lead to different behaviours in the buildings sector and the transport sector.
Educational	<i>Lack of information. Most households have little knowledge of the availability of energy efficient technologies, and if they do, of how those technologies might help them reduce their energy consumption.</i>	<i>Lack of information. There is little knowledge on the precise characteristics of electric vehicles or “green vehicles”.</i>	Markets for buildings energy services and for transport are quite separate, but nonetheless the Belgian federal authority addresses the incomplete information barrier regarding appliances and vehicles with one and the same policy instrument, namely the so-called “energy guzzlers” website.
Economic	<i>Energy prices of electricity, natural gas and heating fuel oil (HFO) do not internalize externalities.</i>	<i>Energy prices of fossil-based transportation fuels do not internalize externalities.</i>	Energy and/or carbon taxes for all kinds of fossil-based fuels in Belgium are too low to have a significant effect on energy (saving) behaviour.
	<i>Lack of access to capital. Home-owners often find it difficult to raise the funds for deep renovation of their dwellings.</i>	<i>Lack of access to capital. Consumers do not have the funds to match the high purchase costs of electric vehicles.</i>	End-users who cannot raise enough capital for energy efficient technologies in the building sector, usually have an even more

			difficult time gathering funds for electric vehicles, as the authorities in Belgium favour subsidies and tax investment credits for the building sector rather than for the transport sector.
Institutional	<i>Fragmentation of authority. Different policy instruments at federal and regional level and within the regions for energy efficiency in the buildings sector.</i>	<i>Fragmentation of authority. Different policy instruments at federal and regional level and within the regions for energy efficiency in transport sector.</i>	Fragmentation of authority prevents the development of an integrated approach, both between the federal level and the regions, in-between the regions, and intra-regional.

1.2 ASSESSMENT OF IMPACT OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

Deliverable 2.2 of work package 2 in the HERON project requires a qualitative assessment of cross cutting barriers, taking into consideration number of different resources that identified the same barrier; the number of sub-sectors that were linked with the same barriers; the easiness with which the barrier can be confronted; the duration of the barrier; and the number of different policy instruments that were linked with the same type of barrier.

For Belgium, this is extremely difficult if not impossible to accomplish, for the following two reasons:

- Firstly, the number of empirical studies addressing barriers is already very low; and for the most part focused on (residential) buildings.
- Secondly, none of the existing studies addresses both sectors at the same time. In fact, energy efficiency studies on buildings and transport sectors are completely separate from each other. A barrier identified in the Belgian context is therefore always linked to one sector, and one sector only (either buildings or transport sector, but never both at the same time).

Our assessment in table 2 is therefore by necessity purely based on expert knowledge.

Table 2 Assessment of cross-cutting barriers

Impact of barriers	Description of barrier
High	Low priority of energy efficiency
	Attitude-Action gap
	Social interactions
	Lack of access to capital
	Energy prices that do not internalize externalities
	Fragmentation of authority
Medium	Imperfect information
	Heterogeneity of end-users
Low	<i>No low impact barriers assessed</i>

1.3 POLICIES ADDRESSING CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

Concerning the number of policy instrument that were linked with the same type of barrier, the answer is one: the federal “energy guzzlers” website. Of course, similar types of policy instruments (e.g. fiscal incentives) are used for both sectors, but one particular policy instrument never aims to address both buildings and transport. In essence, this is the result of the most typical institutional barrier for Belgium, namely the “fragmentation of authority”. This is explained in detail in HERON deliverable D1.1 country report for Belgium. In the following paragraph, we recapitulate those findings from D1.1.

There is a severe fragmentation of policy instruments. This is the case for the buildings sector, but even more so for the transport sector. If there is such a thing as a energy efficiency “strategy”, the unauthorized version would be this. All three regions in Belgium focus on buildings, both residential and non-residential (although dwellings appear to receive somewhat more attention). The energy efficiency policies and measures for the transport sector are weak, if not to say very weak. Basically, transport policies are limited to either agreements with the federal and regional public transport operators on improving vehicle fleet efficiencies and travel efficiency including interconnectivity; financial support for alternative modes of transport (bicycles in particular); and informative measures combined with financial / fiscal instruments to promote purchasing cars that emit less CO₂. The promotion of electric mobility is generally speaking lacklustre. In the Flemish Region and the Walloon Region ambitious mobility plans are still in the making. The expected (and long overdue) mobility plans intend is to integrate mobility with spatial planning (land use).

In other words, there is no connection what so ever between energy efficiency policies addressing the buildings sector and the transport sector.

For the identified “cross-cutting” barriers that have already been addressed by policies in Belgium, *albeit separately*, we refer to HERON Deliverable D2.1 country report for Belgium.

1.3.1.1 The “energy guzzlers” website

As already stated, there are no energy policies in Belgium addressing both the buildings sector and the transportation sector at the same time.

The one exception is the informative federal “energy guzzlers” website, where indeed information is provided to the Belgian consumers for both energy efficient appliances and energy efficient vehicles available on the Belgian market.

The Federal Public Service (FPS) Health, Food chain Safety and Environment; Directorate-general for Environment (DG5) - Climate Change Section, department of Product Management and Chemicals and the thematic service “climate change” developed the website and maintain it.

The real reason for the existence of this website is not so much the existence of a deliberate cross-cutting policy, but rather the fact that the FPS Health, Food chain Safety and Environment is responsible for product policies in Belgium. All information at the website is therefore related to “energy efficiency” products.

CHAPTER 2: KEY FINDINGS

Concerning cross-cutting barriers for Belgium, the key findings are as follows:

- There is no known research or literature that addresses the issue of cross-cutting barriers in Belgium. All research focuses on either the building sectors or the transport sector, but never both.
- Based on our expert knowledge, we identified a number of barriers that *might* be called cross-cutting, but again we have to emphasize that there is no “hard” empirical evidence for this.

The *potential* cross-cutting barriers we identified for Belgium are:

- Social, cultural and educational
 - Social interactions – credibility and trust (behavioural aspect of information dissemination)
 - Low priority (of energy efficiency) – other attributes (are more salient)
 - The attitude – action gap (related to environmental values)
- Economic
 - Imperfect information, more in particular lack of information
 - Heterogeneity across end-users
 - Limited access to or lack of access to capital
- Institutional
 - Low energy and transport related taxes (i.e. energy prices do not internalize negative externalities)
 - Fragmentation of authority

Concerning “cross-cutting” energy policies in Belgium, again we have to be very clear: there are *none* in Belgium. All policies either address buildings or the transport sector, but never both at the same time. This is probably and at least partly the result of the “extreme fragmentation of authority” in Belgium, both inter-regional and intraregional, and which was identified as one of the most important institutional barriers in Belgium (see HERON deliverable D1.1 country report for Belgium, D1.2 country report for Belgium and D2.1 country report for Belgium).

There is but one policy instrument that addresses both the building sector and the transport sector, namely the federal informative “energy guzzlers” website. This is mainly because it was set up by the Federal Public Service Health, Food chain Safety and Environment, who are responsible for “product policies” rather than energy policies. The fragmentation of authority becomes even more apparent in Belgium, when considering that the regions also have an informative website on environmentally friendly vehicles; totally disconnected from the energy guzzlers website.

REFERENCES

There is to our knowledge no empirical research literature on cross-cutting barriers in Belgium. We refer to the country reports for Belgium in the Heron project for a description of barriers and policies specific to Belgium.

HERON D1.1 LANDSCAPE OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY PACKAGES IN A MULTI-LEVEL GOVERNMENT SYSTEM PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT NATIONAL REPORT FOR BELGIUM SEPTEMBER 2015

HERON D1.2 STATUS-QUO ANALYSIS OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICIES IN 8 EU COUNTRIES D 1.2. PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT NATIONAL REPORT FOR B

HERON D.2.1 WORKING PAPER ON SOCIAL, ECONOMIC, CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL BARRIERS IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT WITHIN EACH PARTNER COUNTRY-NATIONAL REPORTS, DATE 27 JULY 2015 Belgium National Report

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.2.2

MAPPING AND CATEGORISING OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

30 SEPTEMBER 2015

Partner: Black Sea Energy Research Centre

Bulgaria

National Report

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

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ACRONYMS

EE	Energy efficiency
EU	European Union
MRDPW	Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works
n/a	Not available
SEAP	Sustainable Energy Action Plan
VAT	Value Added Tax

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report grounds on the findings of the national report “D2.1 Working paper on social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in buildings and transport within each partner country-National Report for Bulgaria”. It presents a part of D2.1 report’s contents with the aim to identify the cross-cutting barriers to the implementation of energy efficiency in the buildings and transport sectors.

After the conducted research it became clear that both sectors – buildings and transport have only a few cross-cutting and more sector-specific barriers. The identification of the common barriers will allow the setting of common objectives for their overcoming.

The identified cross-cutting barriers have high and medium impact on the energy efficiency. No crossing points have been observed between the barriers with low impact. The barriers, which will be examined in more details in this report, are:

Medium impact:

- Buildings:
 - *Lack of information;*
- Transport:
 - *Lack of information regarding green transportation;*

High impact:

- Buildings:
 - *Lack of finance;*
 - *High costs;*
 - *No incentives for EE projects;*
- Transport:
 - *Lack of finance;*
 - *Lack of economic stimuli for purchasing electric/hybrid vehicles.*

The outcomes of this report, together with D2.1 will be used to inform WP3 and WP4. The main barriers identified for each country and affecting demand in both in buildings and transport sectors, will be included in the scenarios that will be developed for both sectors in participating countries and compared using the LEAP software.

CHAPTER 1: MAPPING CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

1.1 SOCIAL, CULTURAL, EDUCATIONAL, ECONOMIC AND INSTITUTIONAL CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS IN BULGARIA

The mapping and categorization of cross-cutting barriers across the buildings and transport sectors is undertaken to inform Task 2.2.

The results of the investigations that have been presented in D2.1, show a few crossing points between barriers in buildings and transport sectors in Bulgaria. Despite their different core and common benefits for the environment, there are no policies or instruments addressing both sectors. The types of barriers that do not cross in buildings and transport are social, cultural and institutional.

The common for both selected sectors barriers are of educational type. The missing or not appropriately presented information is a precondition for the low level of awareness regarding climate change and environmental issues. In the buildings sector this causes denial of energy efficiency opportunities. The factors that affect the uninformed decisions are the lack of instruments to raise the awareness and the absence of policy to support them. Most of the people consider the energy efficiency renovation as unworthy of the investment, because of the high initial costs and the uncertainties of the investment payback period. In Bulgaria the electricity prices are the lowest in the EU, which favours the choice of air-conditioning systems as heating source and make the consumers cut off their district heating installations. Usually people do not consider bigger investments in the energy performance of the house/dwelling unless it is very necessary. Another side of this barrier is the lack of capacity in loan lenders in the field of energy efficiency, which leads to unavailability to assess the risk of the long – term investment. Regarding the transport sector, the passengers do not give account of the damages caused to environment due to their transportation habits and driving behaviour. In the both cases, the low literacy results in denial to change certain habits and undertake corrective measures. The car buyers usually take into account the efficiency of the car, but do not intend to invest more in energy efficient vehicles even if the payback period is not long for them. There is a serious need also for information campaigns for transportation modes and their effects on the environment. Passengers often do not consider the pollution they create, when using alone their private vehicles.

The high initial costs of the EE measures implementation in buildings and of the investments in efficient mobility, and the lack of economic incentives have highest impact among the barriers. The last are the main reasons for the lack of energy efficiency market expansion and occurrences of market failures. There is no common financial or other type of instrument to support its overcoming, but several one-to-one measures address these issues in both sectors. In the building sector most of the people need equity for the planned renovations. Large share of the projects cover the bank engagement by money from the energy savings, which possess high risk for the debt repayment. This barrier is addressed through the National Programme for Energy Efficiency in Multi-Family Residential Buildings (MRDPW 2015). The measure is 100% funded by the State and it concerns only

housing blocks with more than 36 apartments. Although no cost is involved for the buildings' owners, in many cases they demonstrate suspicion and lack of interest. The initial costs impede the investments in EE and one of the reasons for not understanding the benefits is the low level of electricity prices in Bulgaria. Many home owners also do not want to use loans for such investments and leave the home improvements for later, when these issues are more urgent. There are no official data at state level on the type of vehicles (as age, type of engine, fuel consumption, etc) that are used for transportation of passengers or delivering of goods, but the majority of people buy used cars, while new vehicles are preferred by people, who have reached certain social status.

In the economic barriers is stated the problem with no incentives for building renovation, when higher energy efficiency class is reached and no incentives for purchasing hybrid or electrical vehicles. Presently the instrument for building renovation stimuli is the building tax fee exemption if the building increases its energy performance to higher class and it is only for several years depending on the certification. This instrument needs to be revised, because it is not attractive of comparing the tax saving to investments costs. In the public transport sector, local authorities invest in efficient vehicles through grant programmes and own budget. Most of the large Bulgarian cities have renewed a significant share of their transport fleet, but this is not enough to attract back the majority of the population.

The high price of the modern and efficient vehicles and the low level of income predetermine the wide use of old and inefficient cars. The stimuli for increasing the purchases of electric or hybrid vehicles include exemption from registration and annual taxes, parking fees (for now only in the capital Sofia) and vignette taxes. There are no economic supporting schemes as premiums of the purchasing value or reduction of VAT. Other countries' good practices show that sufficient financial stimuli makes the more efficient vehicles more preferable for the buyers. These cross-cutting barriers do not have a common policy instrument to tackle down their limitations to the market uptake.

The common barriers are shown in the next

Table 1.

Table 1 Cross-cutting barriers across buildings and transport

Types of barriers	Barriers in building sector	Barriers in transport sector	Description
Social	<i>n/a</i>	<i>n/a</i>	There are no cross-cutting social barriers
Cultural	<i>n/a</i>	<i>n/a</i>	There are no cross-cutting cultural barriers
Educational	<i>Lack of information</i>	<i>Lack of information on green transportation</i>	The information is either insufficient or not appropriately presented, which leads to a low level of awareness on climate change and environmental issues.
Economic	<i>Lack of finance</i>	<i>Lack of finance</i>	Higher initial costs impede investing both in implementation of EE measures in buildings, and in more efficient and environmentally friendly vehicles.
	<i>High costs</i>		
	<i>No incentives for EE projects</i>	<i>Lack of economic stimuli for purchasing electric/hybrid vehicles</i>	The only stimulus for EE improvements in the buildings sector is the tax reduction under certain conditions. The purchase of environmentally-friendly vehicles is supported by exclusion of payment of certain taxes. These are not considered enough attractive and economically feasible.
Institutional	<i>n/a</i>	<i>n/a</i>	There are no cross-cutting institutional barriers

1.2 ASSESSMENT OF IMPACT OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

The impact of the described cross-cutting barriers on the energy efficiency is presented in Table 2. The assessment is based on the methodology proposed by KEPA.

Table 2 Assessment of cross-cutting barriers

Impact of barriers	Description of barrier
High	Lack of finance (transport sector)
	Lack of economic stimuli for purchasing electric/hybrid vehicles
	Lack of finance (building sector)
Medium	No incentives for EE projects (building sector)
	Lack of information (buildings)
Low	Lack of information on green transportation
	n/a

1.3 POLICY INSTRUMENTS ADDRESSING CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

The lack of finance and of incentives has highest impact among the barriers. These are treated by the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, EU funds, national/local budgets, other financial mechanisms, grants, subsidies. The National Action Plan on Climate Change addresses the lack of incentives in transport sector

The national policy framework on EE, local/regional policy framework on EE, SEAP (Covenant of Mayors) are addressing the lack of information in both sectors. The barriers and the addressing policy instruments are presented in the following Table 3.

Table 3 Cross cutting barriers and relevant policy instruments

Types of barriers	Cross-cutting barriers	Building sector: current policy instruments	Transport sector: current policy instruments
Social, cultural and educational	Lack of information	National policy framework on EE, Local/Regional policy framework on EE, SEAP (Covenant of Mayors)	National policy on EE in transport sector
Economic	Lack of finance	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, EU funds, National/Local budget, other financial mechanisms, grants, subsidies	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, EU funds, National/Local budget, other financial mechanisms, grants, subsidies
	High costs	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, EU funds, National/Local budget, other financial mechanisms, grants, subsidies	-
	No incentives for EE projects	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, EU funds, National/Local budget, other financial mechanisms, grants, subsidies	National Action Plan on Climate Change

CHAPTER 2: KEY FINDINGS

The described in the previous chapter barriers correspond to the results of the investigations, carried out by BSERC and presented in D2.1. Due to the specifics of the barriers in the two sectors, only few crossing points are observed.

The lack of finance and of economic incentives affects both sectors and has the highest influence on the energy efficiency in the country. These are closely connected with the poor financial possibilities of the greater part of the population, which cannot afford investing in EE improvement of their properties and in efficient and sustainable vehicles. Although these barriers are addressed by a number of national action plans and various financial instruments, still they are not enough to change the situation. The energy efficiency legislation should decisively target the barriers through cross-sectoral framework implementation.

On the other hand people usually do not sufficiently trust the funds, because of the corruption practices and the need “to know someone” if you want your job to be done properly. This is equally in force for the both sectors. The policies and their instruments need a proper execution and appropriate control measures should be put into practice.

Another crossing point refers to the lack of information regarding climate change and the influence of human behaviour on the environment. The lack of information is assessed at having medium impact on the EE in the country.

The stated cross-cutting barriers’ importance shows the need of common policy framework implementation, which will support and effectively inspire the initiation of energy efficient activities by all stakeholders.

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MAPPING AND CATEGORISING OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

30 SEPTEMBER 2015

Partner: *Stockholm Environment Institute Tallinn Centre*

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National Report

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

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ACRONYMS

KredEx	Financing institution
LEAP	Long range Energy Alternatives Planning System
MEAC	Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communication
PV panel	photo-voltaic solar panel
SUV	Sport utility vehicle

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides the contents of the Estonian national report which seeks to identify cross-cutting barriers to the implementation of energy efficiency across buildings and transport sectors.

The material collected will be used to inform D.2.2 “Mapping and categorising of cross-cutting barriers across buildings and transport sector”. The outcome of these reports will also be used to inform WP3 and WP4.

The main cross-cutting barriers which affect the future demand in buildings and transport sectors were identified based on Deliverable D.2.1 for Estonia. The cross-cutting barriers will be included in the scenarios modelled by the LEAP software and compared with those of other participating in the project countries.

In Estonia there are plenty of cross-cutting barriers affecting simultaneously the buildings and transport sector. Just to emphasize some most common cross-cutting barriers one could refer to the educational barriers category identified in D.2.1. Common in both, in the building and transport sectors, is the lack of qualified specialists who would be able to plan and develop integrated sectoral policies and, partly depending from this, the fragmentation of the policy implementation. Also, in the institutional barriers category the fragmentation of the policy implementation between some governmental institutions as well as different stakeholders could be emphasized.

Some of the cross-cutting barriers listed in this report, have already been addressed within the current policy instruments. These are mainly to do with awareness raising, willingness of public to invest in energy efficiency whilst indeed the dependence on public investment is rather high, as well as lack of local specialist.

CHAPTER 1: MAPPING CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

1.1 SOCIAL, CULTURAL, EDUCATIONAL, ECONOMIC AND INSTITUTIONAL CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS IN ESTONIA

The cross-cutting barriers identified for Estonia fall under categories of social, cultural, economic, educational and institutional setup. Some of the common denominators are aspects such as the institutional incapability, insufficient national investment support, the inadequate co-operation between some of the institutional levels like local and regional municipalities, etc.

In the following table, only the cross-cutting barriers are exposed. These have been selected out based on the work performed in the Deliverable 2.1. The barriers identified in Deliverable 2.1 were each re-phrased into one barrier common for buildings and transport sector. In the description column, the relevance of each common barrier to buildings and transport sector has been described.

Table 1 Cross-cutting barriers across buildings and transport

Types of barriers	Barriers in buildings sector	Barriers in transport sector	Description (how these barriers affect each sector)
Social	<i>Increasing client/ consumer wellness</i>	<i>Increasing client/ consumer wellness</i>	People always wish to own bigger houses, bigger cars, if a certain wellness status has been achieved. Thus, it can be stated, that increasing consumer wellness generates higher energy both in transport and buildings sector. In transport sector particularly there is significant social pressure for SUV-s and powerful passenger cars. In both sectors energy efficiency is expected to decrease in line with the increase in wellness.
	<i>Willingness to pay for more energy efficient alternatives</i>	<i>Willingness to pay for more energy efficient alternatives</i>	The low income of aged people in Estonia as well as an overall poor image of public transport (quite often it is considered as if public transport is for low income people) leads to the low demand of energy efficient alternatives taken to practice. There is a general low willingness of public to pay for public transport and to invest in green energy (for instance in buildings sector people often lack money to refurbish their homes).

Cultural	<i>Energy usage habits</i>	<i>Energy usage habits</i>	Estonia has quite an autonomous energy market thanks to the abundant domestic fuel and oil shale. This makes the price of energy relatively low due to historically weak tradition to save energy (leading to high energy consumption). In transport sector the negative user habit is the consumer preference of relatively powerful and big cars, aggressive/ speedy driving style which also leads to higher energy consumption thus decreasing the energy efficiency.
	<i>Energy intensity in relation to Estonian cold climate</i>	<i>Energy intensity in relation to Estonian cold climate</i>	Estonian winters tend to be rather rough and cold, causing high energy demand for heating. In transport sector this means more driving during the winter, triggering people to own even more powerful passenger cars, particularly in rural areas where the road maintenance is inadequate.
Economic	<i>Size of the country and low population density</i>	<i>Size of the country and low population density</i>	Small scale solutions are quite often relatively expensive. Here the size of the country and small population density of Estonia (about 30.3 people per km ²) plays quite some role as investment is needed also for low populated small local areas and these tend to be costly. In Estonia there is regionally fragmented energy saving potential – some bigger cities such as Tallinn and Tartu have higher population density and higher income, whilst other have low population density and lower income.
	<i>Dependence on private investment</i>	<i>Dependence on private investment</i>	The dependence on private investment is too high compared to government priorities and investments which tend to be inconsistent in energy efficiency policies. Yet, more sufficient national investment schemes would encourage growth in road sector. Also, in terms of buildings sector, in order to get the KredEx financial support for the energetic refurbishment, the tenants need to be financially eligible for

			the support scheme. This makes the achievements to be made in energy efficiency largely depending on private investments.
	Settlements structure	Settlements structure	There is relatively high energy demand due to settlements structure. The summer houses / second homes of Estonians are often located in low density areas where there is no proper bus or train connection, forcing people to buy cars. The same goes for the buildings sector where in some areas it is more difficult to achieve the energy efficiency of the buildings. This can be for instance due to the half empty apartment buildings due to increased unemployment in some low populated areas which sets more difficult conditions for the apartment building cooperatives to take common action.
Educational	Lack of appropriate knowledge among public and low awareness	Lack of appropriate knowledge among public and low awareness	Low awareness about energy efficient options/ alternatives both in buildings and transport sector. In buildings sector there is still low awareness of tenants and property owners in terms of more energy efficient technologies (lack of relevant easily understandable to all tenants information) and other alternative options available. Also in transport sector the benefits of cycling is more seen as a sports and leisure activity rather than using bicycle as a mean of transport in everyday life (going to school, work, etc.). Public lacks appropriate knowledge on economic gains of energy efficiency of buildings and energy sector in general.
	Lack of relevant national schemes	Lack of relevant national schemes	Lack of knowledge on indoor air quality and health effects in buildings sector as well as lack of integrated transport and land-use planning. In general, more national guidance and proper schemes would be needed.

	<i>Lack of highly qualified specialists</i>	<i>Lack of highly qualified specialists</i>	Not enough high-level trained specialists in energy efficiency, also insufficient number of construction companies with experience of low energy buildings. In transport sector there is a sharp need for integrated transport/mobility and planning professionals.
Institutional	<i>Hard to find common ground in agreements between different administrative levels, and stakeholders (e.g. MEAC and the Ministry of Environment)</i>	<i>Hard to find common ground in agreements between different administrative levels, and stakeholders (e.g. MEAC and the Ministry of Environment)</i>	Quite often it is the case, that the work concerning the buildings sector has been split between too many different administrative levels, making it hard to find common understanding in principal issues. Transport/mobility sector management is split between several departments, leading to lack of integrated governance in general.
	<i>Lack of co-operation between local municipalities</i>	<i>Lack of co-operation between local municipalities</i>	Lack of sufficiently integrated transport and land-use planning and lack of co-operation between local governments in general. Instead of learning from each other, local municipalities tend to compete with each other.
	<i>Operational overlap and lack of clarity</i>	<i>Operational overlap and lack of clarity</i>	Administrative fragmentation and lack of integrated governance

1.2 ASSESSMENT OF IMPACT OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

Based on the table above, new barriers common to both sectors were formulated. The classification to high and medium was performed following the methodology¹ given for the completion of this specific report. Out of all the barriers identified, none of them had low impact. Therefore, it can be concluded that the barriers identified here, are also the barriers with the most significant impact. The results can be seen in Table 2 below.

Table 2 Assessment of cross-cutting barriers

Impact of barriers	Description of barrier
High	Increasing client/ consumer wellness
	Size of the country and low population density
	Dependence on private investment
	Settlements structure
	Lack of co-operation between local municipalities
Medium	Willingness to pay for more energy efficient alternatives
	Energy usage habits
	Energy intensity in relation to Estonian cold climate
	Hard to find common ground in agreements between different administrative levels, and stakeholders (<i>e.g. MEAC and the Ministry of Environment</i>)
	Lack of highly qualified specialists
	Lack of relevant national schemes
	Lack of appropriate knowledge among public and low awareness
Operational overlap and lack of clarity	
Low	<i>Not identified</i>

¹ Methodology to perform the assessment of the cross-cutting barriers in this report, was based on the guidelines given by the project manager of HERON responsible for Deliverable 2.2.

CHAPTER 2: KEY FINDINGS

One of the most obviously common barriers in both buildings and transport sectors, is lack of specialists, who could plan, implement, promote and monitor integrated sectoral policies. It could be noticed at national and also local level. Nevertheless, the number of high level experts in universities, research institutes and private enterprises is increasing from year to year, the energy efficiency new requirements still need more people to carry on and implement the most updated information in buildings sector. Considering the continuously growing interest to energy efficient buildings, the construction of new modern, low energy consumption houses has boosted in Estonia for more than five years ago (Energy ..., 2015). There are good examples of low energy and passive houses design and construction for apartment houses, private houses and also office buildings using renewable energy equipment like PV-panels, solar collectors and heat pumps to reduce significantly the energy consumption (SENSE passiivmajad ..., 2015). Also, the information dissemination and public awareness are on their way up. Quite a lot has been done, still it is the beginning of long-lasting process towards the energy efficiency wider deployment all over the country.

As for transport sector the educational background related professionals and civil servants do not fully support energy efficient transport system. High level professionals are still scarce, therefore road engineering oriented or civil servants employed with not relevant educational background. Trend in the sector is still positive as the educational background of transport planners and civil servants is getting more relevant and diverse. Also, there are more opportunities for degree studies abroad for the university students.

Still, city planners together with architects transport and mobility research labs are collaborating to find new approaches in organising the living environment in bigger towns and capital city Tallinn. In September 2015 the international architecture festival "Tallinn Architecture Biennale Self-Driven City" devoted to self-managing city with the emphasis on smooth organisation of transport was launched and various activities including mobility issues, town planning, buildings energy efficiency etc. last for more than a month (Self-Driven ..., 2015).

From the institutional barriers identified in D 2.1., common in both in the building and transport sectors, is the fragmentation of the policy implementation between government institutions and different stakeholders. Each stakeholder is responsible for the tiny part of the policy implementation, thus sometimes policy actions are driving in different directions or even are contradicting each-other. E.g., in buildings sector the management and integration of operational activities in energy efficiency and the relationship with the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications (MEAC) are unclear. The relationship between the MEAC, and the Ministry of the Environment and operational programmes should be restructured to remove operational overlaps and improve consistency. Estonia should consider creating an energy efficiency unit, which would be able to commission, research, evaluate and implement energy efficiency priorities maximising delivery efficiency, reporting to the Energy Department in the MEAC. The latter should lead co-ordination of energy efficiency policies across government to merit required focus and operational clarity. The Estonian Renewable Energy Association has drafted a proposal to streamline and centralise the procedures: to

have an authority (a one-stop shop) that would facilitate all the processes for renewable energy project developers (International Energy Agency, 2013). Both on national and regional level, the management of transport and mobility issues is split between different ministries, state level departments and on local level – municipal departments. For example in Tallinn transport planning issues are split between 4 different departments – Urban planning department (spatial planning and building permits), Transport Department (public transport management, traffic and parking management), Public Works Department (cycling policy, building of infrastructure), Environmental Department (environmental assessment, emission and noise reduction, promoting sustainable transport). On the national level, the institutional capacity lies mainly in Road Administration (responsible for national road network, traffic safety, minor role in regional PT planning) (Jüssi et al., 2014; Rannala et al., 2013).

The cross-cutting barriers already addressed in current policy instruments are: 1. Low awareness; 2. Willingness to pay for more energy efficient alternatives; 3. Lack of highly qualified specialists; 4. Lack of relevant national schemes; 5. Operational overlap and lack of clarity. Yet it must be underlined that most of them are not addressed in direct way, but rather in an indirect manner. All of the mentioned barriers have to a certain extent been integrated to the yet to be proved National Energy Management Development Plan 2030+. This is a freshly formulated document (relevant national scheme) which combines all the energy efficiency related documents so far into one comprehensive strategy. The 5 highlighted barriers common in buildings and transport sector as just listed above, are the ones addressed in one way or another to the mentioned development plan. These are also the topics what the national government is currently most well aware of, trying to work on their elimination. Lack of capacity is also tackled via national planning guidance – a national guidelines document is being worked out by the ministry of Interior to increase the capacity of local governments to tackle issues related to energy efficiency, sustainable mobility and planning. Low awareness and lack of specialist have been addressed through setting up new study programmes in different universities across the country, directly dealing with the topics related to energy efficiency in buildings and transport sectors. Also trainings and seminars have been organised for public in order to raise awareness. The willingness of public to invest in more energy efficient technologies and other methods which would increase the overall national energy efficiency (for instance home refurbishment) is currently helped via support schemes of Foundation KredEx (which is an authority giving out financial support for electric vehicles, apartment cooperatives and home owners in general). This is increasing the willingness of public to pay for energy efficiency measures since through the financial support given, the prices have been made cheaper. On the other hand, the national financing schemes are still rather weak as well as the interest of public to invest despite of the support already given. This is so, because for the successful funding application to be made, one needs to comply with certain conditions (such as proof of certain income). Thus the barriers - dependence on private investments, as well as – willingness of public to pay (low incomes particularly), counteracts to a certain extent with the KredEx support given. Also raising fuel excise duty on motor and heating fuels (planned increase by ca 30% 2016-2018) is a common fiscal instrument for tackling these barriers.

The barriers listed up above are rather common for most of the fast developing countries in former centrally planned economies. It is a matter of time and effort to smoothly overcome these.

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MAPPING AND CATEGORISING OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

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ACRONYMS

BAT	Best available technology
BAFA	Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle, Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export control
BfEE	Bundesstelle für Energieeffizienz, Federal Department for Energy Efficiency
BMVI	Bundesministerium für Verkehr und digitale Infrastruktur, Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure
BMWi	Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie, Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy CO ₂ – Carbon dioxide
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EU	European Union
ITDP	Institute for Transportation and Development Policy
KBA	Kraftfahrtbundesamt, Federal Motor Transport Authority
KfW	Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau, Bank for Reconstruction
LEAP	Long range Energy Alternatives Planning System
PJ	Petajoule
SME	Small- and medium-sized company
SRU	Sachverständigenrat für Umweltfragen, Council of Experts for Ecologic Questions
UBA	Umweltbundesamt, Federal Environment Agency
VAT	Value-added tax
WP	Working package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report identifies cross-sectoral barriers influencing the uptake of energy efficiency by hindering energy efficiency enhancing investment or behaviour decisions for Germany. The analysis is based on findings of the national report for Germany to inform D2.1.

The analysis shows that the comparability of the buildings and transport sector is limited. Just over one third of barriers identified in D2.1 can be framed as being cross-sectoral. Many barriers with a high impact listed in D2.1 are sector specific, thus are not included in the cross-sectoral assessment. However, several cross-sectoral barriers for Germany have been identified (listed below) of which some are clusters of several sector-specific barriers. Because none of the barriers is of low impact in both sectors, the list does not include barriers of low impact.

High impact:

- Limited relevance of energy consumption and environmental performance
- High up-front costs of energy efficient technologies
- Policy-induced and/or not yet dissolved disincentives by policy
- Missing financial resources in the public sector and adverse long-term effects

Medium impact:

- Lack of awareness of energy consumption and CO2 emissions
- Investment lock-in
- Payback period for energy efficient technologies
- Lack of awareness of other co-benefits

None of the identified cross-sectoral barriers are found to be addressed by one policy covering both sectors. However, in most cases the listed barriers are addressed by at least one sector-specific policy.

The material collected in this report is used to inform D.2.2 'Mapping and categorising of cross-cutting barriers across buildings and transport sector'. The outcome of the report is also used to inform WP3 and WP4. The main barriers identified for each country and affecting demand in both in buildings and transport sector will be included in the scenarios that will be developed for both sectors in participating countries and compared using the LEAP software.

CHAPTER 1: MAPPING CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

1.1 SOCIAL, CULTURAL, EDUCATIONAL, ECONOMIC AND INSTITUTIONAL CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS IN GERMANY

The research questions to be addressed in this report are: *Which of the typology-specific barriers identified in D.2.1 are common in both the buildings and transport sector? How does each of these barriers affect each sector?*

The question how the barriers affect each sector has been already addressed by the national report to inform Deliverable 2.1¹. Therefore this report only provides a summary of findings for the two sectors. In general, the national report to inform Deliverable 2.1 has shown that manifold barriers exist in Germany. Barriers of all category types, ranging from social, cultural, educational, economic and institutional, have been found.

In this sense, the term “cross-cutting” can be interpreted in two ways. The focus of this report is to identify barriers that apply to the buildings sector as well as to the transport sector (further referred to as cross-sectoral barriers). In addition, “cross-cutting” can be also interpreted in the sense of cross-cutting between different types of barriers such as economic, cultural or institutional barriers.

The country report for Germany has already shown that the typology of barriers is not always strict, and various interrelations exist - already for the case of single sectors. For instance, the owner-tenant (investor-user) dilemma in the buildings sector has been grouped as an institutional barrier, however, it has implications on the incentive structure and therewith also has an economic dimension. This leads to cross-cuts in the typology of the identified barriers between the two focus sectors. Besides, how barriers are discussed in the literature can have an effect on the framing of barriers.

Concerning cross-sectoral barriers, it needs to be stressed that the two sectors themselves have different fundamental characteristics, making a one-to-one translation of single barriers often meaningless. One of the most important sector-related structural difference is that transport naturally relates to mobility and therewith to stronger infrastructural needs (e.g. roads, airports) in comparison to buildings. Linked to that there is a stronger influence of governmental decision in this sector, e.g. on infrastructure expansion, influencing modal shift decisions of individuals. On the side of buildings, the complexity of individual investment decision processes, particularly in the case of building retrofits, is a main challenge. Thus, in some cases only clusters of barriers could be found. Some barriers found for one sector might also be relevant for the other though it has not been listed either because there is no evidence available for the respective barrier or the principles by which the barrier influences the efficiency of the two sectors are quite different. For instance, age has a clear

¹ D.2.1 working paper on social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in buildings and transport within each partner country – national report for Germany

influence on private energy efficiency investments in the buildings sector (i.e. decreasing willingness to invest in energy efficiency measures), while the relationship between age and investments in vehicles is mixed. On the one hand, the majority of new vehicles which tend to be more energy efficient are owned by people older than 50 years, while used vehicles are more common among younger people. On the other hand, also the engine size of the vehicle is connected with the age of its owner: younger people tend to own vehicles with smaller engine size (KBA, 2011).

In the following, the identified cross-sectoral barriers influencing the uptake of energy efficiency by hindering energy efficiency enhancing investment or behaviour decisions are briefly described. Findings are based on the literature review and expert knowledge of the Wuppertal Institute for sectoral barriers (see national report to inform Deliverable 2.1).

Cross-sectoral barrier (cultural): Limited relevance of energy consumption and environmental performance

For both sectors a limited relevance of energetic quality and environmental performance is found. Private individuals often decide on renting/ owning a house or flat based on other attributes than energy standards, so a relative unimportance of energetic quality and environmental performance can be derived. For the case of transport, quantitative evidence indicates that the importance granted by potential vehicle buyers to energy efficiency and environmental performance is decreasing over time.

- *Barrier identified for buildings “Disadvantage of energetic quality to other attributes of a housing unit”*: The energetic quality of an apartment or house is currently seen as less important than other attributes of dwellings, e.g. balcony, garage, a modern bathroom etc. (Hacke & Lohmann, 2006).
- *Barrier identified for transport “Limited relevance of environmental performance and energy efficiency in vehicle purchasing”*: In 2011, only 47% of potential vehicle buyers rate the vehicle’s CO₂-emission level as important or very important and there is a tendency towards less importance. In 2009, this criterion was important or very important for 59% (Aral, 2011).

Cross-sectoral barrier (educational): Lack of awareness of consumed energy and CO₂ emissions

In the case of buildings and transportation a lack of awareness of consumed energy and CO₂ emissions is found. Households often underestimate potential energy savings and therewith savings in CO₂ emissions related to their building. For the case of transportation, a small fraction of car owners knows of CO₂ emissions. In both sectors, investments as well as behavioural measures could reduce energy consumption and therewith CO₂ emissions.

- *Barrier identified for buildings “Misperception of building condition (bounded rationality)”*: A survey among single-house owners finds that 85% of owners see their house in a good condition and not see any actions required. Stieß et al. (2010) find that approx. 60% of respondents experience their building to have a good energetic condition. However, their

perception of the energetic standard often differs from political objectives and BAT standards (e.g. triple instead of double glazing of windows) (Krmer et al., 2005).

- *Barrier identified for transport “Lack of awareness of fuel consumption and emission of own vehicles” and “Limited awareness of the energy consumption of goods deliveries among private consumers”*: According to Aral (2011), only 8% of car owners know the average CO₂ emission level of their own car. The awareness of own vehicle emissions is decreasing compared to findings from 2009. In addition, consumers lack awareness of the energy consumption of their purchases and respective deliveries (e.g. due to online shopping) (Bhler-Baedeker et al. 2013).

Cross-sectoral barrier (cultural/ educational/ economic): Lack of awareness of other co-benefits (e.g. comfort gains, wider sustainability benefits, quality of life)

Energy efficiency improvements often lead to several co-benefits such as increase of comfort, liveability or safety related aspects, which are not properly taking into account in the decision making process, partly, due to a lack of awareness. While in the buildings sector this applies mainly to the individual, in the transport sector, co-benefits have to be seen from a societal perspective. A high level of private motorized modes leads to adverse effects such as noise pollution, traffic accidents and cities crowded with cars. A shift to energy efficient public transport offers the potential to improve the quality of life in cities.

- *Barrier identified for buildings “Lack of awareness of non-energy benefits”*: One main reason why energy efficiency actions are not successful are information deficits and thus a general lack of awareness on the possibility to gain benefit from non-energy attributes. Building appearance, comfort and energy costs savings, value maintenance and the increase of value are seen as major benefits (Schle et al. 2011; Friedrich et al., 2007; Novikova et al., 2011).
- *Barrier identified for transport “Limited focus on energy efficiency and co-benefits in the public decision-making”*: Public decision-making in transport focuses often on short-term savings of travel time leading to the expansion of road infrastructure. This is also reflected in the way in which the costs and benefits of transport projects are appraised. Wider effects such as impacts on quality of life or comfort are not reflected in the appraisal (Hging et al., 2014).

Cross-sectoral barrier (cultural, economic): High up-front costs of energy efficient technologies

Several energy efficiency improvement actions require high up-front costs. Independent of the payback period, these can constitute a highly relevant barrier as additional capital needs to be raised leading to shifts in expenditures and savings. In this context, it appears that energy efficient building solutions have a stronger link to debt financing than in the case of transport. This can be explained with relatively higher associated investment requirements.

- *Barrier identified for buildings “High up-front costs, lack of capital and missing profitability”*: Private households, housing units, municipalities and (particularly smaller) companies face

this barrier. High up-front costs are often linked with the necessity to borrow capital, however for the case of Germany Krémer et al. (2005) found that 75% of dwelling owners finance retrofitting measures with equity capital. According to Stieß et al. (2010), nearly half of asked respondents (residential) answered that equity capital for investments is missing. Existing programmes in Germany address this barrier by providing grants and loans. Albrecht et al. (2010) name an aversion of homeowners to borrow capital for retrofits.

- *Barrier identified for transport “Limited willingness to accept higher purchasing prices for an energy efficient vehicle” and “Limited willingness to accept high costs for alternatively fuelled vehicles (e.g. electric vehicles)”*: In a survey by BMUB and UBA (2015), 87% of the respondents were of the opinion that electric vehicles are too expensive. According to Aral (2011), only 57% of potential vehicle buyers would accept surcharges of 1,000 Euro (or more), but 91% would accept 500 Euro additional costs for a more energy efficient vehicle. According to a study conducted by Bozem et al. (2013), costs are important criteria in vehicle purchasing decisions. If cost of alternatively fuelled vehicles were comparable to those of diesel and gasoline vehicles, 80% of respondents would consider switching to a vehicle running on alternative fuels.

Cross-sectoral barrier (economic): Payback period for energy efficient technologies

Investment decisions often depend on the expected payback period of measures (often linked to risk aversion). For both sectors this is found to be of importance as investments are more frequent in cases of short payback periods (2-3 years) than in the case of long payback periods (10 years and more).

- *Identified barrier for buildings “Length of payback period”*: Friedrich et al. (2007) find that approx. half of private investors are willing to invest in measures which redeem after 5 years. If the payback period grows to 12 years, the share of respondents drops to 3%. In the buildings sector payback periods can often amount to ten years and more. Besides private persons, length of payback period is also found to be of high importance for investments by smaller companies and the public sector (e.g. municipalities) (BfEE, no year; BAFA, 2012).
- *Identified barrier for transport “Payback period of fuel efficient vehicles”*: While investments in energy efficient vehicles result in considerable economy-wide benefits over the lifetime of a vehicle, they may not create sufficient payback rates for individuals responsible for vehicle purchasing decisions. Most car buyers do not account for costs-savings from efficiency beyond 2 to 3 years (Lah, 2015).

Cross-sectoral barrier (institutional, economic): Policy-induced and not yet dissolved disincentives by policy

Under this cross-sectoral barrier, several identified barriers are clustered. Disincentives or adverse incentives that impede energy efficiency in the buildings and transport sector appear on local, regional and national level.

- *Identified barriers for buildings “legal barriers”, “complexity and target conflicts of support programmes” and “missing incentives by single policies”*: Legal requirements impeding energy efficiency cover e.g. distance to property lines and compliance with existing preservation for historic buildings (Weiß & Dunkelberg, 2010). In Germany, several support programmes are available. Though policies are introduced, to e.g. lower financial burdens, the number and complexity of programmes make it difficult for households and companies to decide which programme/combination of programmes are most beneficial (Krémer et al., 2005, Schüle et al., 2011). Furthermore, the different programmes addressing buildings from different perspectives (e.g. energetic refurbishment, barrier-free refurbishment, urban development, protected buildings) are not coordinated well. Thus, the programmes support single issues neglecting the targets of neighbouring programmes. E.g. the urban development programme “Soziale Stadt” supports the design and painting of facades, but at the same time it is interdicted to use KfW funds for energetic measures on the same building. Concerning missing incentives, for instance, the German “Energieausweis” (energy performance certificate) has to be in place for renting and selling buildings. But in practice it has very little power, is rarely asked for and does not include obligations for energetic refurbishment.
- *Identified barriers for transport “Tax policies that negatively affect road transport energy efficiency”, “tax policies that favour inefficient modes” and “Parallel extension of road networks”*: Some tax policies in place in Germany are suggested to have potentially counterproductive effects on transport energy efficiency. The option to deduct commuter travel from income tax negatively affects individual travel behaviour. There is a fixed rate of kilometre travelled that can be deducted from income tax. This tax benefit is considered to provide unjust benefits car based commuter travel. This is for instance because the maximum limit of deductible costs can be increased if the commuter uses a private car (UBA, 2010). Tax incentives for house ownership and building are also considered to contribute to urban sprawl and incentivise commuting by car (Tscharaktschiew & Hirte, 2012). In addition, the current tax system privileges air travel compared to rail. VAT is not imposed on international flights, whereas cross-boarder rail services are subject to VAT. In addition, rail operators have to pay fees for the use of tracks and stations, while aviation benefits from subsidised take-off and landing fees (UBA, 2014).
Also public infrastructure investment decisions often do not favour energy efficient modes. Despite the strategic objectives to increase rail and waterborne transport, often there is a parallel investment in road infrastructure that is continuously extended (BMVI, 2015).

Cross-sectoral barrier (economic, institutional): Missing financial resources in the public sector and adverse long-term effect

Missing financial resources on local and regional level (particularly municipalities) lead to unfavourable public investments in public facilities and a lack of public investments in infrastructure for sustainable transport modes. This can lead to higher financial burden of the same in the long run.

- *Identified barrier for buildings “Adverse long-term effect of municipality investments”:* Municipalities in consolidation of public budget need to present a financial plan to the federal government. Higher investments as necessity for the energetic refurbishment of public buildings usually are interdicted due to financial constraints even if they might be beneficial for the public budget in the long term.
- *Identified barrier for transport “Lack of financial resources for high-quality public transport”:* For urban public transport there is a rising discrepancy between growing passenger numbers and investments in public transport. Many German municipalities have a tight budget and the continuation of federal funding for public transport provision is currently under revision, so that expansion of public transport remains undone (UBA 2014).

Cross-sectoral barrier (institutional): Investment lock-in

Buildings and transportation are both sectors with high infrastructural investment needs. Regarding the buildings sector, this means that the renovation and replacement cycle can lead to lock-ins, particularly if investment decisions do not fulfil the highest available energetic standards (BAT standard). For the transport sector, the lock-in period highly depends on the specific subject. Fleet renewal periods lead to lagging uptake of energy efficient vehicle technologies. However, investments in transport infrastructure influence the sector’s performance for much longer periods.

- *Identified barrier for buildings “Investment lock-in in private, commercial and public buildings”:* The average renovation cycle of buildings in Germany is 30 to 60 years (Kohler, 2012). This leads to a significant time lag until new and efficient technologies can materialise in the building stock.
- *Identified barrier for transport “Investment lock-in of vehicle owners”:* The average age of passenger cars in Germany is about nine years (KBA, 2015). Consequently, there is a significant time lag until new and efficient technologies have fully penetrated the vehicle fleet.

Table 1 summarizes the identified cross-sectoral barriers, their type of barrier and the sector-specific barriers from which these have been derived from.

Table 1 Cross-cutting barriers across buildings and transport²

Types of barrier	Barrier(s) in building sector	Barrier(s) in transport sector	Description
Cultural	<i>Disadvantage of energetic quality to other attributes of a housing unit (cultural)</i>	<i>Limited relevance of environmental performance and energy efficiency in vehicle purchasing (cultural)</i>	Limited relevance of energy consumption and environmental performance
Educational	<i>Misperception of building condition (bounded rationality) (mainly educational)</i>	<i>Lack of awareness of fuel consumption and emission of own vehicles (educational)</i> <i>Limited awareness of the energy consumption of goods deliveries among private consumers (educational)</i>	Lack of awareness of energy consumption and CO ₂ emissions
Cultural, educational, economic	<i>Lack of awareness of non-energy benefits (value) (cultural/ educational)</i>	<i>Limited focus on energy efficiency and co-benefits in the public decision making process (economic)</i>	Lack of awareness of co-benefits, e.g. comfort gains, wider sustainability benefits, quality of life
Cultural, economic	<i>High up-front costs, lack of capital and missing profitability (economic)</i>	<i>Limited willingness to accept higher purchasing prices for energy efficient vehicles (cultural)</i> <i>Limited willingness to accept high costs for alternative fuelled vehicles (e.g. electric vehicles) (cultural)</i>	High up-front costs for energy efficient technologies
Economic	<i>Length of payback period</i>	<i>Payback period of fuel efficient vehicles</i>	Payback period for energy efficient technologies
Institutional, economic	<i>Legal barriers (institutional)</i> <i>Complexity and target conflicts of support programmes (institutional)</i> <i>Missing incentives by single policies (institutional)</i>	<i>Tax policies that negatively affect road transport energy efficiency (economic)</i> <i>Tax policies that favour inefficient modes (economic)</i> <i>Parallel extension of road networks (institutional)</i>	Policy-induced and/or not yet dissolved disincentives by policy
Institutional, economic	<i>Adverse long-term effect of municipality investments (institutional)</i>	<i>Lack of financial resources for high-quality public transport (economic)</i>	Missing financial resources in the public sector and adverse long-term effect
Institutional	<i>Investment lock-in in private, commercial and public buildings (institutional)</i>	<i>Investment lock-in of vehicle owners (institutional)</i>	Investment lock-in

² In brackets it is indicated how the sector-specific barriers are framed in the national report for Germany to inform D 2.1.

1.2 ASSESSMENT OF IMPACT OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

In a second step, the identified cross-sectoral barriers are qualitatively assessed in terms of their impact on energy efficiency ranking from ‘high’ to ‘low’. This estimation is based on the ranking made for single sector-specific barriers.

Following criteria have been taken into consideration for the assessment: (1) the number of different resources that identified the same barrier and, (2) the number of sub-sectors that were linked with the same barrier, (3) the easiness by which the barrier can be overcome and (4) its persistency in terms of duration of its appearance.

The ranking approach of the cross-sectoral barrier is divided into two steps. First, under the assumption that transport and buildings are of the same relevance, the rankings assigned to the individual sectoral barriers in 2.1 were first compared. Cross-sectoral barriers were ranked according to the following principle:

- adoption of the D2.1 ranking if the related barriers are ranked similarly in both sectors
- if one barrier is ranked one category higher in one sector, the lower ranking was taken
- If the related barrier was ranked high in one sector and low in the other, a medium ranking was adopted

According to the overall result of this assessment step, all identified cross-sectoral barriers receive a medium ranking. In the case of some barriers there are large sectoral discrepancies related to the ranking, e.g. “misperception of building condition” is of high importance in the buildings sector, however “lack of awareness of fuel consumption and emission of own vehicles” has a low sectoral ranking. In the second step, only cross-sectoral barriers are taken into account and these are ranked relative to each other in the set of cross-sectoral ones. The internal ranking of cross-sectoral barriers leads to the results displayed in Table 2.

Table 2 Assessment of cross-cutting barriers

Impact of barriers	Description of barrier
High	Limited relevance of energy consumption and environmental performance
	High up-front costs of energy efficient technologies
	Policy-induced and/or not yet dissolved disincentives by policy
	Missing financial resources in the public sector and adverse long-term effects
Medium	Lack of awareness of energy consumption and CO ₂ emissions
	Investment lock-in
	Payback period for energy efficient technologies
	Lack of awareness of other co-benefits

All cross-sectoral barriers have been ranked as medium or high. Moreover, many barriers that are ranked high in D2.1 are not identified to be cross-sectoral. Consequently, it occurs that barriers ranked as medium in D2.1 might be ranked high in the cross-sectoral ranking due to the limitation of barriers considered in the ranking.

1.3 POLICY INSTRUMENTS ADDRESSING CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

None of the identified cross-sectoral barriers are found to be addressed by a policy covering both sectors. However, in most cases the listed barriers are addressed by at least one sector-specific policy. Table 3 lists all of the identified barriers as well as policies by which these are addressed.

Table 3 Cross-sectoral barriers and relevant policy instruments

Barrier(s) in the building sector	Policy instruments addressing the buildings sector barrier(s)	Barrier(s) in the transport sector	Policy instruments addressing the transport sector barrier(s)
<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Limited relevance of energy consumption and environmental performance</i>			
Disadvantage of energetic quality to other attributes of a housing unit (cultural)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy saving ordinance • On-side energy consultation • Energy checks • Energy consultation for SMEs • KfW construction monitoring 	Limited relevance of environmental performance and energy efficiency in vehicle purchasing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CO2-related motor vehicle tax
<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Lack of awareness of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions</i>			
Misperception of building condition (bounded rationality) (mainly educational)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspection of boilers and heating/cooling installations • Seal of quality efficiency house • On-side energy consultation • Energy checks • Energy consultation for SMEs • Energy performance certificate 	<p>Lack of awareness of fuel consumption and emission of own vehicles (educational)</p> <p>Limited awareness of the energy consumption of goods deliveries among private consumers (educational)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passenger car labelling • “me and my car” campaign; • “new driving” campaign • Heavy goods vehicle toll charges
<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Lack of awareness of other co-benefits (e.g. comfort gains, wider sustainability benefits, quality of life)</i>			
Lack of awareness of non-energy benefits (value) (cultural/educational)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On-side energy consultation • Energy checks • Energy consultation for SMEs • Promotion of energy management systems 	Limited focus on energy efficiency and co-benefits in the public decision making process (economic)	

Table 4 cont. Cross-sectoral barriers and relevant policy instruments

<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: High up-front costs of energy efficient technologies</i>			
High up-front costs, lack of capital and missing profitability (economic)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevant KfW programmes • Market incentive programme to promote the use of renewable energies in the heating market • BAFA cross-cutting technologies • Energy tax 	<p>Limited willingness to accept higher purchasing prices for energy efficient vehicles (cultural)</p> <p>Limited willingness to accept high costs for alternative fuelled vehicles (e.g. electric vehicles) (cultural)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federal funding programme for energy efficient commercial vehicles to be launched in 2016 (BMW, 2014) • Tax benefits for natural and liquid gas; • Tax exemption for electric vehicles
<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Policy induced and/or not yet dissolved disincentives by policy</i>			
<p>Legal barriers (institutional)</p> <p>Complexity and target conflicts of support programmes (institutional)</p> <p>Missing incentives by single policies (institutional)</p>		<p>Tax policies that negatively affect road transport energy efficiency (economic)</p> <p>Tax policies that favour inefficient modes (economic)</p>	
<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Missing financial resources in the public sector and adverse long-term effects</i>			
Adverse long-term effect of municipality investments (institutional)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding programmes for municipalities 	Lack of financial resources for high-quality public transport (economic)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal transport financing act and regionalisation act: financial aid for investments for improvement of the infrastructure and the transport of passenger in cities and municipalities
<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Investment lock-in</i>			
Investment lock-in in private, commercial and public buildings (institutional)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indirectly addressed by all instruments 	Investment lock-in of vehicle owners (institutional)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CO2-related motor vehicle tax

CHAPTER 2: KEY FINDINGS

The analysis shows that the comparability of the buildings and transport sector is limited. Just over one third of barriers identified in D2.1 can be framed as being cross-sectoral and many barriers with a high impact listed in D2.1 are sector specific, thus are not included in the cross-sectoral assessment. However, several cross-sectoral barriers for Germany have been identified (listed below) of which some are clusters of several sector-specific barriers. Because none of the barriers is of low impact in both sectors, the list does not include barriers of low impact.

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- Payback period for energy efficient technologies
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MAPPING AND CATEGORISING OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

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National Report

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ACRONYMS

EC	European Commission
EE	Energy Efficiency
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
ESCO	Energy Services Company
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
Ministry of T&C	Ministry of Transport and Communications
NZEBs	Nearly Zero Energy Buildings
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SEAPs	Sustainable Energy Action Plans
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
WP	Work Package
YPEKA	(Greek interpretation) Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides the cross-cutting social-cultural-educational, economic and institutional barriers across the building and transport sectors in Hellas. The barriers for both sectors are observed in two multi-governance levels: national and local/regional. In the local/regional, the barriers were mostly linked with the initiative of Covenant of Mayors and the implementation of Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAPs) (buildings, mobility) and concerned the local authorities.

The cross-cutting barriers are analyzed and assessed. There are common barriers that affect clearly both sectors (i.e. the economic barrier “financial crisis”), others that concern different types of technologies in the two sectors (i.e. the social-cultural-educational barrier “negative public perception for green roofs and electric vehicles”), and others that, despite the different origin of the barrier, they have the same result (i.e. the social-cultural-educational barriers “Negative past experience & disappointment for a new system” adversely affects the installation of innovative technologies in both sectors).

The most prominent cross-cutting barriers are the inefficient performance of the implementation network/governance framework (institutional barrier), the low availability of information (social-cultural-educational barrier), the low state of support (institutional barrier) and the low prioritization of EE (institutional barrier).

The assessment of the identified common barriers into high-medium-low, in terms of their impact, provides a clear picture of the current situation and will assist in the effort to incorporate barriers encountered by end-users into energy modeling and to identify those policy mixtures that are more effective in tackling these barriers.

CHAPTER 1: MAPPING CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

1.1 SOCIAL, CULTURAL, EDUCATIONAL, ECONOMIC AND INSTITUTIONAL CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS IN GREECE

In the Hellenic report of Deliverable D2.1 “*Working paper on social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in buildings and transport within each partner country*”, such barriers for Hellas are mapped and analysed.

The barriers for both sectors are observed on two multi-governance levels: national and local/regional. In the local/regional, the barriers were mostly linked with the initiative of Covenant of Mayors and the implementation of Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAPs) (buildings, mobility) and concerned the local authorities.

There are no available large-scale surveys concerning behavior of the different Hellenic social groups towards energy efficiency policies and technologies. Most of the official reports, funded research projects and published research papers are addressing the building sector, while a small group concerned transport sector, mainly the road passenger sub-sector.

Cross-cutting barriers – common barriers in both sectors – were observed and further analysed in Table 1, along with a description of the policy instruments that target the cited barriers.

Table 1 Cross-cutting barriers across buildings and transport

Types of barriers	Barriers in building sector	Barriers in transport sector	Description (how these barriers affect each sector)
Social – Cultural – Educational	<i>Lack of environmental consciousness, awareness, culture</i>	<i>Low environmental sensitivity & Lack of “green transport behaviour”</i>	<p>The <i>lack of environmental consciousness/sensitivity/behaviour</i> is a common barrier for both sectors as described below:</p> <p><i>Building sector</i> - This barrier had a negative affect on the promotion of Energy Efficiency (EE) actions in this sector from the side of end users since more than 2/3 of the Hellenic population did not believe that their buildings were responsible for environmental degradation (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). In combination with the fact that the government did not provide information or gave incentives to the public to invest in sustainable development, relevant EE actions were not undertaken by end-users.</p> <p>The barrier concerns the national policy for EE as a total. No specific policy instrument addresses it yet.</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> - Due to low environmental sensitivity, the citizens were not contributing to the promotion of sustainable mobility modes nor would they adopt mobility initiatives (CityMobil2, 2013; CRISP project, 2012).</p>

			No specific policy instrument addresses it. Proposals from municipalities might improve the situation.
	Low level of awareness	Low public awareness towards eco-driving Limited knowledge on public transport	<p>The low level of awareness is a common barrier for both building and transport sectors, as it is described below.</p> <p>The common element is that end-users of both sectors have not realized the benefits that EE technologies/practices can bring into their daily life.</p> <p><i>Building sector</i> – The low level of awareness regarding the benefits of energy conservation and sustainability in buildings combined with the low awareness of the new technologies and their benefits in buildings (residences, hotels etc.) prevented the endorsement of EE in this sector (Theodoridou I. et al., 2013; Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011).</p> <p>It is worth mentioning that researchers showed that in different areas in Greece, users who considered themselves well-informed on energy saving were more likely to have installed more energy efficiency devices, than others (Zografakis N. et al., 2012). But, other surveys revealed very low percentages in technologies (energy labelling) used by households in Kastoria (35,8% of the 271 responders reported use of “A” energy class electrical devices) (Christidou C. et al., 2014). Respectively, a survey in 685 companies’ managers in Crete pointed out that only 9,8% were using Inverter technology of air-conditioning split units, while 44,2% of those who had not installed it were willing to do so (Tsagarakis P.K. et al., 2012).</p> <p>So, as a conclusion: There were cases through which it was clear that the Greek society was unaware about: i) the environmental, economical and EE benefits that would result from relevant technologies. In addition fear for such technologies along with restricted financial incentives reinforced the barrier (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). ii) energy savings due to the use of EE devices (Zografakis N. et al., 2012). iii) Technologies and their benefits for hotels, policy framework or examples from other countries where similar initiatives for hotels were applied (Maleviti E. et al., 2012; 2011; Hotel Solutions, 2011).</p> <p>This is a barrier concerning the National policy for EE as a total. No specific policy instrument is currently implemented to address the barrier.</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> – Correspondingly, low public awareness in eco-driving and Public Transport information hinders the implementation of EE in the transport sector (ECOWILL project, 2010; Ad Personam project, 2009; 2010).</p> <p>There are no specific instruments in the legislation for increasing awareness about eco-driving.</p>
	End-users aloofness due to negative past experience	Disappointment for new transport systems	<p>Negative past experience and disappointment for a new system adversely affects the installation of innovative technologies in both sectors.</p> <p><i>Building sector</i> – Negative past experiences (either</p>

		<p>historical and fading or recent and persistent) with solar thermal systems, ground source heat pumps, quality problems in thermal renovations, underperformance of air source heat pumps etc. prevents end-users to choose innovative EE technologies. (ENTRANZE, 2014).</p> <p>No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> – Consumers in Greece are wary towards innovative technologies in transport, such as electric vehicles due to negative past experience on innovative technologies (used in other sectors) and need to be convinced about the robustness of these ones (YPEKA, 2012).</p> <p>No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.</p>
Negative public perception for green roofs	Negative public perception towards electric vehicles	<p>Each of the two sectors has to face a negative perception against a specific technology.</p> <p><i>Building sector</i> – There was negative public perception for Green roofs (programme launched in 2011). Green Roofs were not as popular as expected due to high capital investment and to disagreement among the owners of the building (CRISP project, 2012).</p> <p>This is a barrier concerning the National policy for EE as a total. No specific policy instrument addresses it yet.</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> – The electric vehicles have not yet gained the trust of consumers regarding their technologic robustness (ECOWILL project, 2010). No policy instrument is addressing the barrier, apart from financial incentives mentioned in D.1.2.</p>
Established perception for hotels that high energy use will ensure the comfort of guests	Perception that owning and driving a private car shows the status symbol and good lifestyle	<p>The common element for this barrier is <i>the established perception</i>, differentiated accordingly for each sector.</p> <p><i>Building sector</i> – The owners of hotels as end-users have the perception that high energy use is necessary to ensure the comfort of guests and do not proceed with EE actions (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). Another established perception that hoteliers had was that hotel units based in a natural and sensitive environment (i.e. islands or mountainous areas) affect the environment while those units located in the city centre of Athens do not. If they were aware about the carbon footprint that occurs from the energy consumption of their facilities, perhaps they would had a different perception (Maleviti E. et al., 2012; 2011).</p> <p>This barrier affected the implementation of the Energy Performance Certificate and the development of the ESCO market. The incorporation of Directive 2012/27/EU will probably improve the situation for this sector.</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> – For many people owning and driving a private car represents a status symbol for good lifestyle, comfort and freedom. This is a barrier in case of policies</p>

			<p>related to congestion charges and strategies towards collective use of mobility services and hinder the shift to more sustainable mobility modes (public transport) (CRISP, 2012).</p> <p>This barrier affected the implementation of planning policy instruments for traffic management. No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.</p>
	<p>Lack of expertise-incomplete training</p>	<p>Lack of certified instructors and examiners for eco-driving</p>	<p><i>Building sector</i> - There is identified deficiency in technical expertise or incomplete training in the following cases about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) bioclimatic architecture (by civil engineers and architects from the construction process (Karkanias C. et al., 2010)). ii) the design of energy renovation - only few construction companies and workers are familiarized with the correct implementation of energy saving measures under the recent EU Directive¹ (for example avoidance of thermo-bridges or the elimination of water vapour condensation risk on renovations of facades) (CERTus, 2015). This increases the risk of damages and might result to significant reduction of the total performance of the measure. iii) renovations of facades (CERTus, 2015). iii) EE issues in buildings and the usage of RES by the municipality’s technical service staff (CERTus, 2015). Usually, the study for a new building or for renovation is assigned to external partners. Therefore, the choice for using EE improvements is entirely up to the sub-contractor (CERTus, 2015). iv) implementation of the JESSICA initiative in Greece. There was need of training of the officials in the municipalities regarding the preparation of the selected projects (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012). The technical services of the municipality stated that the received education by their staff is imposed as part of the implemented legislation. This fact prevents any type of innovative initiative of the staff regarding the energy and environmental performance/outcomes (CERTus, 2015). v) building installations. Installers and maintainers are usually uncertified (YPEKA, 2014). <p>No specific policy instrument addresses this barrier yet. The Draft Law about the Directive 2012/27/EC is expected to temper the extent of this barrier.</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> - The lack of a network of certified driving instructors and examiners was a barrier for the promotion of eco-driving. The driving instructors and examiners were not obliged to know, teach in depth and examine the eco-driving techniques. It was also obvious</p>

¹ nearly zero energy buildings (Directive 2010/31/EU)

			<p>that some driving instructors and examiners would have objected to the implementation of a potential eco-driving program with relevant testing and certification (ECOWILL project, 2010).</p> <p>The barrier remains since there are no provisions for instructors in the legislation for eco-driving.</p>
	<p>Information barrier towards emerging innovative technologies</p>	<p>Low penetration of ICT from elderly people</p>	<p>The common element for this barrier is the <i>inadequate information about innovative technologies</i>.</p> <p><i>Building sector</i> – Different groups of end-users experienced this barrier:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) owners and members of households: they had incomplete or unavailable information and demonstration examples for the use of cost-effective and energy-efficient technologies. This barrier increases the investment costs in such technologies due to: increased transaction/search costs; increased uncertainty regarding the investment; and due to the risk of lock-in an inappropriate technology (Kounetas K. et al., 2011). ii) SMEs faced information restrictions caused by their size or in other words by their limited available resources. The acquisition of information is an advantage of larger firms. Additionally, the level of information or knowledge acquired by a firm is technology specific. The technology vintage is the key factor determining the heterogeneity underlying the level of knowledge among firms (Kounetas K. et al., 2011). <p>The situation is still not confronted despite the dissemination-awareness policy instruments that have been implemented (EXOIKONOMO KATOIKON, ALLAZO KLIMA, GREEN ROOFS, JESSICA etc). Probably the lack of brochures or accessible information that describes in simple way the benefits of emerging innovative technologies is the core of the barrier.</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> - Because of the relatively low penetration of ICT from elderly people in Greece they may not be able to use and accept easily the new means of transportation (CityMobil2, 2013).</p> <p>No specific policy instrument addresses it yet.</p>
	<p>Working habits</p>	<p>Old habits</p>	<p>The common element is <i>the established routine/habits in daily reality</i>. More specifically:</p> <p><i>Building sector</i> - Personnel such as bank staff consider that it is not practical to turn on/off equipment during the working hours due to heavy work pressure (Spyropoulos N. G., Balaras A. C., 2011). Furthermore, office equipment such as automated teller machines, faxes and digital video recorders DVRs are required in standby mode continuously (Spyropoulos N. G., Balaras A. C., 2011). That is why for working buildings/spaces</p>

			<p>potential energy savings office and electronic equipment under the requirements of the Energy Performance of Buildings (Law 3661/2008 – Common Ministerial Decision 5825/9.4.2010) were not considered (Spyropoulos N. G., Balaras A. C., 2011).</p> <p>The incorporation of Directive 2012/27/EC will probably improve this situation.</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> - Most of the Greek drivers have learned and used to drive inefficiently (ECOWILL project, 2010). Eco-driving was not part of their education as drivers. Their adopted way of driving is enhanced by the poor existing infrastructure such as high traffic jams in cities, bad condition and maintenance of certain roads and lack of special tracks for application of eco-driving trainings (ECOWILL project, 2010).</p> <p>There are no provisions for old drivers in the legislation for eco-driving.</p>
	Zero to low availability of information	Limited knowledge on public transport	<p>The common element is the <i>low availability of information</i>. Information exists, but does not reach effectively the target groups to which it is addressed. More specifically:</p> <p><i>Building sector</i> - There is lack of available information not only for the public institutes regarding their energy consumption, but also towards the citizens regarding the energy renovation of the public buildings. The main reason for this situation is the fact that the government does not actually promote this type of renovation and its relevant information (CERTus, 2015). The buildings renovation is used for achieving the target for nearly zero energy buildings (Directive 2010/31/EU²). Residents/users usually have insufficient information and education, regarding the rational use and management of energy, leading to (YPEKA, 2010): i) installation of individual air-conditioning systems without technical study; ii) use of poor performance devices; iii) non maintenance of the heating system.</p> <p>The relevant Ministry attempted to confront this barrier that emerged during the implementation of the national EE policy with the “Energy Efficiency at Household Buildings” Program (YPEKA, 2010).</p> <p>The barrier was encountered again with the Laws that incorporated the Directives for NZEB and EPBD in national legislation.</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> - Limited knowledge towards Public Transport information among citizens, such as routes,</p>

² http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?ELX_SESSIONID=FZMJThLLzfxmmMCQGp2Y1s2d3Tjwtd8QS3pqdkhXZbwqGwlgY9KN!2064651424?uri=C ELEX:32010L0031

			<p>timetables and fares, was observed. This barrier – for supporting the shift to more sustainable mobility modes (public transport) - was observed generally for EU about public transport. A Greek city, Heraklion in Crete island, took part in the questionnaire delivery (Ad Personam project, 2009; 2010).</p> <p>No specific policy instrument addresses it yet.</p>
Economic	<p><i>Reluctance to pay up front great amount of money and preference to EE investments with short payback periods.</i></p>	<p><i>High initial investment for energy efficient solutions compared to conventional ones.</i></p>	<p>The reluctance to make high investments with long payback period is more visible in the building sector rather than in the transport sector.</p> <p><i>Building sector</i> – Energy efficiency solutions, such as green roofs, double glazing windows and NZEB solutions, are avoided by end-users due to high up-front investments and big payback period (CRISP project, 2012; Tsagarakis P.K. et al., 2012; YPEKA, 2014; CERTus, 2015). Some of the EE options for buildings are considered rather expensive or have high payback periods making them of no practical interest from the point of market acceptability, particularly without any financial support or subsidies (Droutsas K.G. et al., 2014). This is not observed only in end-users behaviour but also in the public sector. Municipalities prefer investments with a payback period up to five years since their financial planning coincides with their tenure of local administration which is five years (CERTus, 2015). Also, school administration prefers cost effective EE interventions with very small payback periods (Dascalaki G. E., Sermpetzoglou G. V., 2011).</p> <p>The financial incentives (subsidies, grants, tax exemptions) can address this barrier.</p> <p>This is a barrier that concerns the National policy for energy efficiency as a total. It is expected to be managed by one of the basic elements of the EPBD and the Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs). EPCs are expected to promote energy efficient technologies through (Gelegenis J. et al., 2014):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Classification of buildings to specific energy performance categories: In this way a higher energy class possibly will lead to a higher rental or selling price of the building/apartment. · commendations included in EPCs about improving the energy performance of the building/apartment using cost- effective ways that will possibly enhance awareness of owners. <p><i>Transport sector</i> – There is reluctance to invest on energy efficient solutions such as electric cars, due to high initial investment costs (YPEKA, 2012; EFECT, 2012).</p> <p>Tax exemptions are set for electric and hybrid vehicles (see D.1.2).</p>
	<p><i>Financial crisis</i></p>	<p><i>Financial crisis</i></p>	<p><i>Building sector</i> – The economic recession resulted in limited EE investments such as NZEB interventions</p>

			<p>(radical building renovation) both in the national and the local level, because of: i) limited national subsidies and bank loans for private investors and public entities (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012; Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013; YPEKA, 2014), and ii) reduction of income (YPEKA, 2014).</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> – The economic recession resulted in people’s reluctance to invest on i) energy efficient solutions such as electric cars, due to high initial investment costs (YPEKA, 2012), and ii) eco-driving training campaigns for employees in the private sector (ECOWILL project, 2010). Also, this recession led to funding lag for the modernization of transport infrastructure (Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006).</p> <p>This is linked with economic recession and any recommendations need to be part of an integrated policy planning.</p>
	<p>Costly innovative technologies for end-users.</p>	<p>Costly energy efficient solutions compared to conventional ones.</p>	<p>The common barrier is the high cost of energy efficiency solutions that resulted in low penetration for such products (EFFECT, 2012).</p> <p>The common element of both barriers is the <i>unaffordable cost of the EE technologies from the perspective of the end-users.</i></p> <p><i>Building sector</i> – This barrier was observed for NZEB technologies such as solar cooling. The low market penetration of solar cooling was due to high cost of this technology (CERTus, 2015).</p> <p>Probably the incorporation of the Directive 2012/27/EU (EPBD) into the national legislation will improve the situation.</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> – This was observed for electric vehicles (CERTus, 2015; YPEKA, 2012).</p> <p>Financial policy instruments (tax exemptions for hybrid and electric vehicles) are foreseen so as to moderate the impact of this barrier (see D.1.2).</p>
	<p>Absence of incentives for buyers</p>	<p>Unattractiveness of sector for private investments due to absence of incentives</p>	<p>The common element in these barriers is the <i>unwillingness to pay</i> from the perspective of the end-users. More specifically:</p> <p><i>Building sector</i> – Contractors have a negative attitude towards the adoption of EE technologies or practices such as the bioclimatic architecture due to the higher total cost of the building which leads to smaller selling profit (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). Also, the proportion of customers willing to invest in bioclimatic buildings is smaller than those selecting conventional ones due to absence of incentives (Karkanias C. et al., 2010).</p> <p>The barrier could be curbed by introducing financial policy instruments (loans, tax exemptions etc). The</p>

			<p>absence of such incentives for bioclimatic buildings extends the presence of the barrier (Karkanias C., 2010).</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> – There are difficulties in attracting private investments for railway projects due to the existing poor infrastructure, the state funding for maintenance and to competitiveness of the other transportation means, mainly road transport (Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006). Also, there are no subsidies for the purchase of electric cars.</p> <p>No policy instrument is addressing this barrier, apart from the tax exemptions for electric and hybrid vehicles (road transport).</p>
Institutional	<i>Lack of urban and land planning</i>	<i>Ineffective urban transportation planning</i>	<p>The common element is the <i>absence of effective urban planning</i> which is differentiated for the two sectors as follows:</p> <p><i>Buildings sector</i> – Due to densely built areas the implementation of bioclimatic architecture is difficult. The lack of wide streets, big sites, and exposed facades, limits the utilization of sun. Additionally, vertical tall buildings with narrow vents along the floors, without any thermal insulation in their walls and roofs and with very few features of traditional Hellenic architecture, dominated the decades of 1960s and 1970s. These buildings generated serious operational problems such as insufficient lighting and poor ventilation, besides their very high energy consumption and the resulting operational expenses (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). There are no proposals for confronting the barrier and improving the situation in the sector.</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> - Ineffective urban planning is causing problems to the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) mass-transportation system, since it fails to displace the car dominance and diminish congestion – related problems (Saliara K., 2014; Ministry of T&C,, 2006). ii) bus network since it is using the same roads with other vehicles, iii) traffic due to the lack of parking control and the traffic management (Ministry of T&C, 2006). iv) charging infrastructure for electric vehicles, making the consumers hesitating for their purchases (YPEKA, 2012). <p>There are no proposals for confronting the barrier.</p>
	<i>Complex and difficult legislation and procedures Lack of legislation for positive policy interactions Lack of central coordination</i>	<i>Non-integrated policies</i>	<p>The common element in these barriers is <i>lack in coordinated efforts for integrated policies</i>. More specifically:</p> <p><i>Buildings sector</i> – The barrier is synthesized by the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) a separate Ministry of Environment was created in October 2009, underlying the absence of focused and dedicated environmental planning by

			<p>the state (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). The new Ministry is actually undertaking the role to coordinate efforts for EE issues and design integrated policies.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ii) End-users such as hotels do not adopt EE technologies or practices due to the lack of any effective national legislative policies in the sector of tourism to supplement the existing instruments in the framework of the UNFCCC and the Kyoto Protocol such as those for energy efficiency (Pieri S. P. et al., 2015). This barrier in combination with the fact that EE is pursued on a voluntary basis, sets energy audits and surveys about reporting the building environmental performance of hotels as a necessary preface that will facilitate policymaking for EE (Pieri S. P. et al., 2015). iii) The nZEB definition has been introduced to the national legislation but only in general terms. Detailed requirements and application in practice are not yet specified (RePublic_ZEB, 2015). In addition, it is suggested to ensure the continued adoption and implementation of measures related to informing and educating consumers so that they choose highly energy-efficient buildings / products and changes their behaviour regarding energy use and consumption (RePublic_ZEB, 2015). iv) The most important gap in EE policies was identified at the public sector since there is not an overall strategy of this sector and there are no targets for the energy consumption of its buildings (Energy Efficiency Watch, 2013). <p>The barrier concerns the whole national EE policy for the buildings. It is still not confronted.</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> - The barrier is mainly the lack of integration between the transportation means and the urban/spatial development strategies that are developed separately (Pitsiava-Latinopoulou M. et al., 2014; Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006). According to the ENDURANCE project, which is still ongoing, Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans are not identified as specific policy instrument in the Greek guidance documents (http://www.epomm.eu/endurance/index.php)</p> <p>No policy instrument is addressing the barrier.</p>
	<p>Low state support</p>	<p>Lack of support schemes</p>	<p><i>Building sector</i> - State support for energy renovations and renewable heating and cooling systems appears to be lower in Greece than in similar south European countries (Italy and Spain) (ENTRANZE, 2014). The barrier concerned the: i) National policy for EE (as a total) and ii) energy audits, energy management systems, energy performance certificates, ESCO market. No policy</p>

			<p>instrument is addressing it.</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> - There is no national support scheme for the purchase of electric vehicles, while: i) there is exemption for hybrid and low- emission vehicles from the registration tax and ii) there are no traffic restrictions in Athens for hybrid vehicles (source: Deliverables of Work Package 1, D.1.1 and D.1.2).</p> <p>No policy instrument is addressing it.</p>
	Low prioritization of EE	Low prioritization of EE	<p><i>Building sector</i> - The EE improvement of municipality buildings is not included in the priorities of the technical services of the municipality (CERTus, 2015). The technical service of the municipality decides to have the building renovation only when there are serious static problems. For any other renovation of up-grading the service can make proposals, but these need to be evaluated by an independent institute, regarding their effectiveness as a mid-term investment of the municipality (CERTus, 2015).</p> <p>According to the employees of a municipality, the financing of the projects that do not improve the daily life of citizens are not a priority for municipalities. The fact that citizens are not informed regarding costs/benefits from EE in public buildings set these possible investments to low priority (CERTus, 2015).</p> <p>No policy instrument or action is undertaken to set the EE in higher priority.</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> - Emphasis was given to the primary long term objectives of the transportation sector which concerned the development of the sector through the improvement of the quality of the offered services and of the basic infrastructure. EE was included and managed as a secondary objective (Ministry of T&C).</p> <p>No policy instrument is addressing it.</p>
	Inadequate implementation network/governance framework	Overlap of responsibilities	<p>The common element in this barrier is the performance of the implementation network/governance structure. It is either inadequate, due to the absence of necessary actions/entities or due to overlapping responsibilities; end-users do not receive the assistance that they need. More specifically:</p> <p><i>Building sector</i> – The following cases show the ineffective performance of the implementation network/governance structure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There was not an appropriate structure to ensure that the proposed EE measures under the programme EXOIKONOMO KAT’ OIKON were actually necessary for each building. This was due to the fact that the country did not have – at that time - a legislative framework regarding energy audits and energy service companies (Remaco SA, 2010). • There are still inadequate Monitoring and Evaluation Processes for the EE policies (ADVANCE, 2014). • There was no institute that could provide

			<p>information about all available financing mechanisms for EE actions. As a result, European policy initiatives and funds are not used adequately by the Hellenic stakeholders (ELENA³, European Energy Efficiency Fund⁴, JESSICA) (based on the work of WP1).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most cities administrations did not know about financial instruments that could be used for the SEAPs (Christoforidis et al., 2013). <p>The barrier was identified for: i) National policy for EE (as a total) and ii) EXOIKONOMO (subsidies). There are no proposals to overcome it.</p> <p><i>Transport sector</i> - More than one authority is responsible for the planning of the system of public transportation in the big urban centers. This is an issue that needs to be resolved and allow integrated urban planning (Ministry of T&C, 2006).</p> <p>No policy instrument is addressing it.</p>
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³ <http://www.eib.org/products/advising/elena/index.htm>

⁴ <http://www.eeef.eu/objective-of-the-fund.html>

1.2 ASSESSMENT OF IMPACT OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

The identified barriers are assessed from 'High' to 'Low' in terms of their impact in energy efficiency, with the following criteria taken into consideration:

- The number of different resources that identified the same barrier (Criterion a);
- The number of sub-sectors that were linked with the same barrier (Criterion b);
- The easiness with which the barrier can be confronted (Criterion c);
- The duration of the barrier (Criterion d);
- The number of different policy instruments that were linked with the same type of barrier (Criterion e).

During this assessment, the comparison of these barriers led to the formation of a scale for each of the above criteria. These scales were used for the classification of the barriers into the three types (high-medium-low).

The outcomes of the assessment showed that most of the cross-cutting barriers for the Hellenic case had almost the same level of impact. For verifying the very close differences in the outcomes, and concluding with the classification in high, medium and low, the conclusions of D.2.1 were taken into consideration for those cases.

Table 2 Assessment of cross-cutting barriers

Impact of barriers	Description of barrier
High	Inefficient performance of the implementation network/governance structure (institutional) (Inadequate implementation network/governance framework - Overlap of responsibilities)
	Low prioritization of EE (Institutional)
	Low state support (Institutional)
	Low availability of information (Social-cultural-educational) (Zero to low availability of information - Limited knowledge on public transport)
Medium	Absence of effective urban planning (Institutional) (Lack of urban and land planning – Ineffective urban transportation planning)
	Lack of coordinated efforts for integrated policies (Institutional) (Complex and difficult legislation and procedures-Lack of legislation for positive policy interactions-Lack of central coordination- Non-integrated policies)
	Lack of environmental consciousness (Social-cultural-educational) (Lack of environmental consciousness, awareness, culture - Low environmental sensitivity -Lack of “green transport behaviour”)
	Creation of negative feelings (aloofness and disappointment) towards the use of new technologies or practices (Social-cultural-educational) (End-users aloofness due to negative past experience – Disappointment for new transport systems)
	Negative public perception (Social-cultural-educational) (Negative public perception for green roofs - Negative public perception towards

	<p>electric vehicles)</p> <p>Inadequate information about innovative technologies (Social-cultural-educational) (Information barrier towards emerging innovative technologies – Low penetration of ICT from elderly people)</p> <p>Reluctance to pay more than a defined amount for EE technologies/practices (Economic) (Reluctance to pay up front great amount of money and preference to EE investments with short payback periods – High initial investment for energy efficient solutions compared to conventional ones)</p> <p>Unaffordable cost of the EE technologies from the perspective of the end-users (Economic) (Costly innovative technologies for end-users – Costly energy efficient solutions compared to conventional ones)</p> <p>Financial crisis (Economic)</p>
Low	<p>Low level of awareness (Social-Cultural-Educational) (Low level of awareness – Low public awareness towards eco-driving – Limited knowledge on public transport)</p> <p>Established perception (Social-cultural-educational) (Established perception for hotels that high energy use will ensure the comfort of guests – Perception that owning and driving a private shows the status symbol and good lifestyle)</p> <p>Deficiency in technical expertise or incomplete training (Social-cultural-educational) (Lack of expertise – Incomplete training – Lack of certified instructors and examiners for eco-driving)</p> <p>Established routine/habits in daily reality (Social-cultural-educational) (Working habits-Old habits)</p> <p>Unwillingness to pay from the perspective of the end-users (Economic) (Absence of incentives for buyers – Unattractiveness of sector for private investments due to absence of incentives)</p>

CHAPTER 2: KEY FINDINGS

The identification and analysis of cross-cutting barriers for two Hellenic sectors - buildings and transport sectors - led to the following key findings. The most prominent cross-cutting barriers – common barriers that were observed for both sectors – are the inefficient performance of the implementation network/ governance framework (institutional barrier), the low prioritization of EE (institutional barrier), the low state of support (institutional) and the low availability of information (social-cultural-educational). The majority of these barriers are institutional but linked with the behavior of the end-user. Their ranking in the barriers of high impact is attributed to the fact that there are limited references about social-cultural-educational barriers. The impact of the barriers for each sector was assessed as a total according to the five aforementioned criteria.

Table 3 Assessed as barriers of high impact for Hellenic building and transport sectors

Cross – cutting barrier	Criteria				
	a	b	c	d	e
Inefficient performance of the implementation network/governance structure (institutional)	At least 2 different types of policy instruments	5 references for both sectors	Whole sectors	Difficult to overcome due to no proposals	At least 9 years
Low prioritization of EE (Institutional)	At least 2 different types of policy instruments	2 references for both sectors	Building subsector, whole transport sector	Difficult to overcome due to no proposals	At least 9 years
Low state support (Institutional)	At least 5 different types of policy instruments	2 references	Whole sector, one sector	Difficult to overcome	Not more than 1 year
Low availability of information (Social-cultural – educational)	At least 5 different types of policy instruments	3 references	Two subsectors, whole sector	Moderate due to activities/proposals	At least 6 years

Note: The criteria are on page 18 of this report and have the same weight. The scales per criterion were: for a criterion, values were from 2 to 5 policy instruments, for b from 10 to 2 references, for c from 1 to 3 sub sectors taking into consideration also if the reference mentioned the whole sector, for d from easy to difficult way to handle and for e from 1 to more than 9 years.

Initially, “the inefficient performance of the implementation network/ governance framework” was identified as a barrier with high impact for the building sector only, but not as such for the transport sector (D.2.1). Now, it is a common barrier of high impact. The “Low prioritization of EE” was not among the barriers of high impact in any of the two sectors, but as a common one its impact was assessed as significant and raises the issue of its confronting. The “Low state support” falls in the same case with the previous one. The “Low availability of information” was among the high barriers of the building sector, but not for the transport sector. As a common barrier its impact was assessed

as high. Almost all common barriers are not confronted by a specific policy instrument. The incorporation of Directive 2012/27/EC is expected to confront a part of them.

The mapping and assessment of the cross-cutting barriers across the building and transport sectors will be used for the development of effective energy efficiency policy mixtures.

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MAPPING AND CATEGORISING OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

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ACRONYMS

EE	energy efficiency
ENEA	Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development
EU	European Union
NEEAP	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan
SEAP	Sustainable Energy Action Plans

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Italy is characterized by few examples of cross-cutting EE barriers existing in the building and transport sector. Most of the common barriers regard general aspects related to the institutional and social/cultural pattern of the Italian context and can be identified in the lack of a well-established culture of saving, in the low degree of environmental awareness, the fragmentation of the different administrative levels with consequent delays in adopting norms and regulations. Besides these, a relevant economic barrier is due to the persistent economic stagnation, which has contributed to reduce both the public as well as the private investment shares in EE, and it makes more difficult to access EE technologies, in particular those characterized by high upfront costs. Despite their general character, these barriers show a relatively high degree of influence, which varies from high to medium level.

At policy level, some policy interventions recently implemented have influence on some of the cross-cutting barriers previously described. In this respect, it is worth mentioning: (i) the creation of the National Energy Efficiency Control Room (Cabina di Regia per l'Efficienza Energetica), within the Ministry of Economic Development in 2015, which aims at coordinating the EE measures and interventions across the different administrative levels; (ii) the economic incentives, which represent effective instruments aimed at increasing the turnover of EE technologies in order to replace or renew the stock of existing buildings, appliances and carbon-intensive vehicles.

CHAPTER 1: MAPPING CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

1.1 SOCIAL, CULTURAL, EDUCATIONAL, ECONOMIC AND INSTITUTIONAL CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS IN ITALY

As mentioned in Deliverable 2.1 Annex 6, the lack of a ‘culture of saving’ as a precondition for successful energy efficiency policy interventions as well as an implicit incentive to invest in energy efficiency represents a first important element that affects both the buildings and the transport sectors. Such negative conditions are supported also by official statistics. Recent surveys conducted by the EU Commission show that although “the vast majority of Europeans also think that it is important for national governments to provide support for improving energy efficiency by 2030”, Italy ranks only slightly below the mean, with only 51% of respondents stating that such a support is “very important” (EU, 2014). In addition, indicators on the environmental awareness here employed as further proxy on the relative perception of energy saving benefits, show also a low rank of Italy with respect to other Member States (compared to the EU mean of 50%, only 43% of 2013 Italian respondents admit to have taken actions to face climate change over the past six months and such a share is decreased with respect to 2011) (EU, 2014)¹. Broadly speaking, these recent data confirm the low perception that Italians show with respect to the importance of energy saving concerns. As a consequence, Italy is characterized by a lack of social and cultural background which acts as an intangible but relevant barrier when policy measures are implemented at any administrative level and in any sector of the population and economy. Broadly speaking, such a lack produces non-virtuous behaviours which vary across different sectors of the population and according to the level of income and education, thus limiting the quality and the size of the policy interventions for boosting EE. In the building sector, official data demonstrate that although the relatively large success of tax deduction program aimed at inducing EE improvements, the majority of the applications received refers to insulated windows, while those implying more pervasive interventions such as roof insulation, thermal heating etc. show relatively less success (ENEA, 2014). Although other types of interventions show higher upfront costs but also more than proportional net economic returns, according to ENEA (2014) Italian population prefer to invest a minor part of their income for marginal EE interventions such as new insulated windows. The same factors determine some limitations for increasing the energy saving in the transport sector and for reducing the amount of carbon-intensive vehicles. In particular, Italians seem to prefer cars for travelling to other environmental-friendly vehicles such as bicycles or public transportation (see also Deliverable 2.1, Annex 6 for further details).

A further general but relevant cross-cutting barrier is constituted by the persistent economic stagnation which affects Europe, and Italy in particular, since 2007² on both the supply and demand side. The sovereign debt crisis has also limited the government’s expenditure capacity thus reducing

¹ Specifically, 1019 interviews which cover about 12,55% of EU population.

² Although some recent official statistics has signalled a growth GDP trend in Italy from 2014 to 2015, although weaker than the EU mean (see Eurostat, 2015).

the budgets of those policy interventions aimed at boosting EE, while the persistent economic stagnation has more and more eroded the private consumer capacity to invest in EE, with negative consequences in both the building and transport sector. In addition, the upfront costs for adopting new more efficient technologies represent a cross-cutting barrier due to both limited expenditure budget as well as to high prices of more energy-efficient goods. Specifically, the effect of economic crisis has limited the private investments for new technologies that often show high initial costs although the net present value of such technologies is demonstrated to be positive in their lifecycle (e.g., high costs of heating pumps in the building sector or the high costs of batteries in the transport sector).

With respect to the cross-cutting institutional barriers, it is possible to identify:

- a lack of homogenous normative schemes, which would provide common legislative frameworks and would allow for univocal interpretation of the adopted measures over time and across different administrations. This translates in policy fragmentation with insufficient and unclear norms and regulations, also due to frequent delays in adopting the EU Directives. In this respect, Italy ranks as one of the most inefficient countries within the group of EU Member States (EU Commission, 2010). Since such a delay affects the first phase of normative process in any sector (that is, the implementation of EU guidelines into national laws and regulations), the negative consequences are equally dampened on both the two EE sectors here analysed;
- dyscrasia due to lack of coordination across different territorial levels (national, regional, municipal). The high regional fragmentation results in complex policy coordination across different administrative levels, which often generates insufficient policy response. Also in this case, this barrier affects in equal measure the transport as well as the building sector;
- related to the previous barrier, there is the high complexity and pervasiveness of Italian bureaucracy, which contributes to lower the transparency and efficiency of the in-force EE measures (e.g., longer times for authorizations, misinterpretation of norms and regulations, corruption phenomena).

Table 1 Cross-cutting barriers across buildings and transport

Types of barriers	Barriers in building sector	Barriers in transport sector	Description (how these barriers affect each sector)
Social	<i>None</i>	<i>None</i>	None
Cultural	<i>Lack of a 'culture of saving'.</i>		Low perception of social EE benefits translates in marginal renewal interventions in the building sector and in low propensity to environmental-friendly transport modes (transport sector).
Educational	<i>Scarce environmental awareness.</i>		
Economic	<i>Persistent economic stagnation.</i>		Both the high upfront costs of technologies as well as the reduced budget for EE investments imply low renewal rate of existing buildings and vehicles stock with more efficient ones.
	<i>Upfront costs and reduced expenditure budget for adopting new more efficient technologies.</i>		
Institutional	<i>High complexity and pervasiveness of Italian bureaucracy.</i>		Negative consequences in any sector in which EE plays a role. Specifically, authorizations for private building renewals as well as potential access to economic incentives for low-carbon vehicles and more efficient appliances are thus negatively affected by this common barrier. This also leads to misperception of EE gains thus acting as a disincentive to benefit from in-force EE policies.
	<i>Dyscrasia due to lack of coordination across different territorial levels (national, regional, municipal).</i>		
	<i>Lack of homogeneous normative schemes for univocal interpretation of norms and regulations.</i>		

1.2 ASSESSMENT OF IMPACT OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

Table 2 summarizes the cross-cutting barriers as identified in Table 1, subdividing them according to their impact (big, medium, small). Given the lack of quantitative comparative assessments on the barriers in literature, we followed the approach of Deliverable 2.1 Annex 6 (Italy), which relies on a qualitative expert evaluation based on the authors' knowledge.

Table 2 Assessment of cross-cutting barriers

Impact of barriers	Description of barrier
High	Lack of a 'culture of saving'.
	Dyscrasia between national, supra-national and local norms (lack of policy coordination).
	Lack of normative schemes.
	Scarce environmental awareness.
Medium	Persistent economic stagnation.
	Upfront costs and reduced expenditure budget for adopting new more efficient technologies.
Low	<i>None identified.</i>

CHAPTER 2: KEY FINDINGS

Given the general nature of the existing cross-country barriers, there are no specific in-force policy interventions in which the aim of simultaneously targeting both the building and the transport sector is explicitly stated. Nevertheless, we can identify a group of policy interventions which takes into account both some of the cross-cutting barriers previously discussed.

With respect to the policy fragmentation and lack of policy coordination, an interesting initiative is the creation of the National Energy Efficiency Control Room (Cabina di Regia per l'Efficienza Energetica), within the Ministry of Economic Development³. Launched in January 2015, it aims to coordinate all the different stakeholders (both in the public and private sectors) and administration levels (national and regional levels) operating in the Italian energy efficiency market. Such an initiative will clearly produce positive impacts on the policy governance, in terms of facilitated bureaucratic procedures, normative simplification and efficiency gains in the policy implementation on both the transport and building sector.

Other integrated policy instruments addressing the institutional barriers are constituted, in order of administrative level, by the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP, last version approved in 2014), by the different Regional Energy Plans as well as by the municipal Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAPs). In particular, the SEAPs represent key documents in which the Covenant of Mayors signatory outlines how it intends to reach its environmental and energy saving targets by defining the set of activities and measures, together with time frames and assigned responsibilities, resulting as multi-sector policy instruments. The Covenant represents a remarkable initiative aimed at involving, on voluntary basis, local and regional authorities in order to promote the adoption of energy efficiency measures and renewable energy sources within the administrative territory through the use of SEAPs. Such an initiative has showed a relevant diffusion within the Italian local administrations⁴.

With respect to the economic barriers represented by the high upfront costs of EE technologies as well as by the economic stagnation which limits the household's expenditure budget for adopting new more efficient technologies, a common policy instrument is represented by the economic incentives. In the case of buildings, the incentive mechanism aims at facilitating the renewal of existing appliances stock and envisages a 65% tax deduction together to a tax bonus for energy efficient furniture and appliances (see Deliverable 1.2, page 16 for further details). A similar mechanism is in force for the transport sector, in which the national government provides subsidies for purchasing low emission vehicles in order to replace the older carbon-intensive ones (see Deliverable 1.2, page 37 for further details).

Given that some of the cross-cutting barriers are not envisaged by the existing set of policy measures, further effort should be devoted to accelerate the adoption process of EU directives and

³ See also Deliverable 1.1, Landscape of energy efficiency policy packages in a multi-level government system. National report for Italy.

⁴ http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/index_en.html

guidelines at national and local level. Such interventions would make both the transport and building sector more responsive to any type of EE regulation. In addition, communication campaigns aimed at enhancing the level of environmental awareness as well as initiatives aimed at informing consumers about the net economic returns deriving from more efficient goods, would constitute effective policy instruments addressing the cross-cutting barriers deriving from the lack of culture of saving. In addition, a higher policy stringency of the monitoring and sanctionary regimes, together to a simplification of the normative scheme for accessing EE incentives, would help reducing the barrier of excessive administrative bureaucracy.

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MAPPING AND CATEGORISING OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

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ACRONYMS

BAT	Best Available Technology
EE	Energy Efficiency
EEAP	Energy Efficiency Action Plan
UN	United Nations

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A substantial economic energy saving potential exists in the buildings and transport sectors, but energy efficiency services market in the Republic of Serbia is less developed compared to EU countries (World Bank, 2014). The objective, reducing final energy demand (improvement of energy efficiency), is affected by numerous barriers which are classified in the following groups: institutional, economic, social, cultural and educational. An analysis of identified barriers indicates that some of barriers influence both, the buildings and the transport sectors.

“Heterogeneity of consumers”, “Social group interactions and status considerations” and **“Inertia”** are social barriers, identified in both analysed sectors. **“Mistrust in new technologies”** and **“Credibility and trust”** are recognized as common cultural barriers, while **“Lack of information, knowledge and experience”** and **“Lack of awareness of the population and local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy”** are cross-cutting educational barriers.

“Low households credit capacity” and related **“Low purchasing power of citizens”**, as well as **“Lack of dedicated financing”** are identified as common economic barriers. **“Institutional Capacity of the Government of Serbia”** and **“Institutional Capacity of the local self-governments”** are crosscutting institutional barriers.

Effect of social cross cutting barriers **“Heterogeneity of consumers”, “Social group interactions and status considerations”** on end user behaviour is evaluated as ‘Low’, while the effect on energy efficiency of **“Inertia”** is evaluated as ‘Medium’. The only common cultural barrier, with ‘Medium’ effect is **“Credibility and trust”/ “Mistrust in new technologies”**.

“Lack of information, knowledge and experience” and **“Lack of awareness of the population and local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy”** are educational barriers with ‘High’ and ‘Medium’ effect. Both cross-cutting economic barriers **“Lack of Dedicated Financing”** and **“Low purchasing power of citizens/Households Credit Capacity”** have ‘High’ impact to implementation of energy efficiency measures in the buildings and transport sectors. **“Institutional capacity of the local self-governments”** is recognized as an institutional barrier with ‘High’ impact on end user behaviour, while **“Institutional capacity the Government of Serbia”** is recognized as ‘Medium’ impact institutional barrier in the buildings and transport sectors.

CHAPTER 1: MAPPING CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

1.1 SOCIAL, CULTURAL, EDUCATIONAL, ECONOMIC AND INSTITUTIONAL CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS IN SERBIA

Although a substantial economic energy saving potential exists in the buildings and transport sectors, the energy efficiency services market is less developed compared to EU countries (World Bank, 2014). In spite of some recent progress, main barriers to energy efficiency improvement remain (Kogalniceanu, 2011):

- Low, regulated energy prices (especially electricity price),
- Lack of individual meters or heat cost allocators for measurement of delivered heat energy (related to the buildings sector),
- Short-term budget planning (one year) in municipalities; this period is too short for energy efficiency investments to be completed and reimbursed from savings.
- Lack of specific legislation related to homeowners associations, which could apply for loans for energy efficiency improvements (in the buildings sector),
- Insufficient awareness of the importance and effects of energy efficiency,
- Insufficient capacity of policy makers,
- High initial investment costs for energy efficient technologies,
- Lack of trained staff in the field of energy efficiency.

Besides main barriers, listed above, numerous other barriers related to energy efficiency improvement in the buildings and transport sectors are identified and explained in the work package 2.1. All barriers were classified in following groups: institutional, economic, social, cultural and educational.

“Heterogeneity of consumers”, “Social group interactions and status considerations” and “Inertia” are social barriers, recognized in both sectors. “Mistrust in new technologies” and “Credibility and trust” are recognized as common cultural barriers in the buildings and transport sector, respectively, while “Lack of information, knowledge and experience” and “Lack of awareness of the population and local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy” are cross-cutting educational barriers. Effects of these barriers to both sectors are presented in Table 1.

However, for full understanding of effects which have been caused by aforementioned barriers, social segmentation and specific country context need to be taken into consideration: risk-of-poverty rate is 24.6%, unemployment rate is approximately 19% while the average salary is € 370 (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2015 a,b), (Stadt Müller, 2014). Also, 13.7% of the citizens don't have primary education, 20.8% have only primary education, 48.9% have secondary education while only

16.6% of the citizens have high and university education (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2015).

In the buildings sector, effects of barrier named "Heterogeneity of consumers" can be recognized during selecting and purchasing of household appliances, while the social group interactions and status consideration are more related to financially more demanding implementation of energy efficiency measures, as heating systems installation or investment in improvements of the energy performance of building envelope components. Effect of "Inertia" in the buildings sector is related to the resist of the citizens to change the behaviour and common practice (for example using a specific heating/domestic hot water preparation system or a specific fuel). Also, at local level, as effects of "Inertia", the lack of energy planning, the lack of consistent implementation of development strategies, the lack of project ideas and developed and realized projects can be reported (Gvozdenac et al, 2012). "Mistrust in new technologies", is closely related to "Inertia", and it mainly reflects on the selection of heating systems and systems for domestic hot water preparation in the households sector. Options based on use of renewables or some other energy sources/fuels, instead of traditionally used, are generally considered as unsafe or unreliable.

In the transport sector, effects of "Heterogeneity of consumers" are the most significant during the passenger cars purchasing. The selection process is governed by the quality, price, efficiency and environmental impact. Also this barrier reflects on the selection between new and used cars. However, in the same time the selection of car determines the affiliation to specific social group, and in that sense "Social group interactions and status considerations" are important. Common practice represents purchasing of used car of higher class, rather the new of lower class car, for the same amount of money. "Inertia" is related to a willingness to make a change in traffic organization in general, in existing public transport system, but also to change habits of drivers, passengers, etc. (Mrkajic V. et al. 2015), (Rankovic Plazinic B. et al. 2014). "Mistrust" as a barrier in the transport sector is generally related to some modes of transport, more than to some contemporary technologies. For example, in Serbia majority of passengers avoid traveling by train, although this is the cheapest mode of transport. Identified reasons (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2007) are delays, low speed, long duration of journey, poor and old infrastructure, unpredictable waiting time, etc.

Common for both sectors is lack of reliable energy consumption data. The World Bank reported that reliable energy consumption data are close to non existent (World Bank, 2010). In addition the differences between official statistics and survey estimations regarding fuel wood consumption indicate a lack of reliable data, which as a consequence hinders the development of appropriate policies (Stadtmüller, 2014). Data reporting system is not disaggregated enough to reflect the energy consumption in more detail (Kogalniceanu, 2011).

Consumers generally lack information which should support behaviour changes related to energy consumption. For example: in Serbia the majority of consumers supplied by district heating systems do not have metering devices, or heat cost allocators as well as the billing information. In such surrounding consumers are not aware of their energy consumption patterns. Also, they do not have information regarding possible reduction of their consumption or about expected benefits of energy efficiency improvement (World Bank, 2010). Besides lack of reliable energy data, little reliable

information and few qualified service providers are major barriers to demand side (World Bank, 2010).

Awareness of energy efficiency is affected by a lack of baseline data and indicators necessary for benchmarking and monitoring. Energy efficiency is just starting to get public attention. (Stadtmüller, 2014) found that in Serbia awareness about the need and benefits of rational energy use depends on economic status of households. There is wide spread opinion among the citizens, that energy is cheap and will remain cheap, while energy efficiency investments are considered as not profitable.

In addition insufficient commitment of decision makers to work and act towards energy efficiency improvement is recognized. It is caused by the limited capacities, resources and the political unpopularity of measures needed to be undertaken. In practice decision makers claim that they are aware of the challenges, but often their commitment is not visible or reflected in official documents, or undertaken measures. In the case of decision makers, long-lasting visions usually don't exist (Stadtmüller, 2014).

It is found that at the level of local self-governments, improvement of energy efficiency depends dominantly on the commitment of the municipality itself. The level of commitment differs according to understanding, awareness, skills, education, priorities and economic state. Increasing the commitment of decision makers in Serbia, towards improving energy efficiency can be reached, if it is recognized as an opportunity for economic development. (Stadtmüller, 2014).

Regarding awareness of consumers, it is concluded that the majority consider energy as public service not as valuable good. Consumers are reluctant to change behaviour, unless it will improve their standard of living (UNDP, 2013).

"Low households credit capacity" and closely related "Low purchasing power of citizens", as well as "Lack of dedicated financing" are recognized as common economic barriers. Effects of these barriers on both sectors are presented in Table 1. The average monthly wages in South East Europe indicate a very low living standard of population. The South East Europe region's average wage is around € 420, and corresponds to one fourth of Germany's average monthly wage, while Serbia's monthly average wage of around € 370, is even lower than the regional average (Stadtmüller, 2014). In such conditions is difficult to invest in improvement of living comfort by implementing energy efficiency measures in households sector, or to purchase a new more efficient car. In the public and commercial sector, lack of dedicated financing and absence of incentives are the primary barriers to successful energy efficiency project realization, especially linked with the low energy tariffs and the unavailability of project financing mechanisms (United Nations, 2010). For the buildings sector, low and cross-subsidized energy prices need to be particularly emphasized. Such surrounding is not favourable for implementation of energy efficiency measures and it does not encourage energy efficiency investments, because it does not provide consumers to save the full cost of energy avoided (World Bank, 2010) (Jefferson Institute, 2009).

"Institutional Capacity of the Government of Serbia" and "Institutional Capacity of the local self-governments" are recognized as common institutional barriers. Effects of these barriers on both sectors are presented in Table 1. Lack of qualified human resources is a major barrier throughout the entire public administration in Serbia, followed with lack of experience in the preparation of projects

to be submitted to funding institutions. (United Nations, 2010), (Kogalniceanu, 2011). Consequently, administrative capacity is in general very limited (Stadtmüller, 2014). The Ministry of Mining and Energy is in charge for both: policymaking and policy implementation. The cross sector nature of energy efficiency cannot be best served in such case. Measures that are targeting transport, public services, etc. are difficult to implement through the only one department of the Ministry in charge for energy. This causes absence of a coherent and consistent strategic approach to energy efficiency improvement (Kogalniceanu, 2011). Lack of administrative capacity (in terms of human resources and training) to implement energy efficiency policy, especially at the local level, has additional influence (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013c).

Table 1 Cross-cutting barriers across buildings and transport

Types of barriers	Barriers in the buildings sector	Barriers in the transport sector	Description (how these barriers affect each sector)
Social	<i>Heterogeneity of consumers</i>	<i>Heterogeneity of consumers</i>	End consumers behave differently because of heterogeneity in preferences. In the transport sector this is related to quality, price, efficiency and environmental impact of selected mode of transport. Even the selection of transport mode (public or personal) shows significant variety inside the same social group (Rankovic Plazinic B. et al. 2014). Additionally, passenger car is often considered as a status symbol. The effect of heterogeneity is present during the selection of origin and characteristics of the vehicle including the selection between new and used (Prvulović et al., 2008). In the buildings sector effects of heterogeneity are identified during the selection and purchasing of household appliances. For some consumers only important for decision-making, is the cost of product (Stadtmüller H. 2014), while some consider only fuel-efficiency of the products, and all expected costs during the lifetime of the products.
	<i>Social group interactions and status considerations</i>	<i>Social group interactions and status considerations</i>	Behaviour of consumers is not always the result of conscious and motivated action. Everyday consumption behaviours are strongly shaped and enforced at the micro-level (Stadtmüller H. 2014). Consumer's decisions are influenced by behaviour of consumers from similar social groups (Rankovic Plazinic B. et al. 2014). Consequently lifestyle has influence on purchase decisions and common practice (Mrkajic V. et al. 2015). Implementation of energy efficiency measures in the buildings sector is mostly limited by experiences within the same social group. Similar financial status within the same social group additionally limits the possibility for implementation of EE measures. On the other side, sometimes positive experience (for

Types of barriers	Barriers in the buildings sector	Barriers in the transport sector	Description (how these barriers affect each sector)
			<p>example, better comfort of the neighbour who improved building's envelope characteristics) makes a positive signal for others from the group to undertake similar measures.</p> <p>In the transport sector, the older citizens have different preferences and habits compared to the younger, regarding using public transport, biking or walking (Mrkajic V. et al. 2015). Also, consumers with lower socio-economic status, for example, prefer using cheap but unreliable intercity train transport, or public transport within the cities, etc. Interactions with friends, families, and colleagues affect the way people make decisions and how they value impact to environment.</p>
	<i>Inertia</i>	<i>Inertia</i>	<p>This barrier represents an absence of motivation to make a change. Consumers resist changing the behaviour and common practice.</p> <p>In the buildings sector, inertia is additionally supported with low purchasing power of consumers (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2015a, 2015b) and low and cross subsidized energy prices (Eurostat, 2015).</p> <p>For the transport sector, effect of "Inertia" is related to the willingness to change traffic organization in general, in existing public transport system, behaviour and habits of drivers, passengers, etc. (Mrkajic V. et al. 2015), (Rankovic Plazinic B. et al. 2014).</p>

Types of barriers	Barriers in the buildings sector	Barriers in the transport sector	Description (how these barriers affect each sector)
Cultural	<i>Mistrust in new technologies</i>	<i>Credibility and trust</i>	<p>Mistrust in new technologies and lack of willingness to adopt energy savings measures make a strong preference for the status quo, due to long-term experience (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011).</p> <p>In the buildings sector, it influences on selection of the heating system (for example, traditional use of biomass in rural areas, or using direct electrical heaters in urban areas are wide spread modes of heating) or the system for domestic hot water preparation (common practice is to use electrical boilers). Other possible solutions are generally considered as unsafe or unreliable (for example, using biomass boilers, geothermal energy, heat pumps or natural gas for heating, or using centralized system or solar collectors for hot water preparation).</p> <p>In the transport sector, mistrust in some modes of transport can be identified. For example, the majority of passengers avoid traveling by train, although this is the cheapest mode of transport in Serbia. Identified reasons (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2007) are delays, low speed, long duration of journey, poor and old infrastructure, unpredictable waiting time, etc.</p>
Educational	<i>Lack of information, knowledge and experience</i>	<i>Lack of information, knowledge and experience</i>	<p>Credibility and trust in the information is of the great importance for decisions. The importance of increasing reliable information about benefits, projects undertaken, examples of good practice are needed both for the population and decision makers (Gvozdenac, et al. 2013). For decision makers lack of knowledge and experience in preparing, carrying out and monitoring phases of the project is pointed out. (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011), (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013c).</p> <p>In general, for the buildings sector, data on energy consumption for subsectors, or even cities or municipalities are usually not available. Most of the cities don't have data about actual energy consumption in buildings (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013c).</p> <p>Energy efficiency have not been not in the focus during the considerations of transport sector</p>

Types of barriers	Barriers in the buildings sector	Barriers in the transport sector	Description (how these barriers affect each sector)
			<p>development (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2007). Data on energy consumption for the transport subsectors at the local level are not available. Most of the citizens are not recognizing energy efficiency as a priority in transport.</p>
	<p><i>Lack of awareness of the population and local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy</i></p>	<p><i>Lack of awareness of the population and local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy</i></p>	<p>Citizens in general support energy efficiency in the buildings sector and recognize it as important, but few have an understanding of what it really means and how to increase energy efficiency in their own homes. Also, most of the citizens think, in current conditions, that energy efficiency projects are unnecessary costs for their municipality or city (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011), (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013c). Energy efficiency in the transport sector is very rare topic in national and local documents (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013 c).</p> <p>Education of population is needed in order to provide basic understanding and benefits from more efficient use of energy. Energy efficiency improvement is usually not a priority for politicians (decision makers). They prefer to choose investments that are more "visible", in order to keep their positions in administration (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011).</p>
<p>Economic</p>	<p><i>Households credit capacity</i></p>	<p><i>Low purchasing power of citizens</i></p>	<p>The average monthly salary in Serbia is app. €370 (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2015b), while available household budget in 2013 (monthly average per household) was app. €470 (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2013). This reflects on purchasing power of citizens, as well as to households' credit capacity.</p> <p>When buying, most of the citizens are deciding dominantly based on the price/cost of the product/service.</p> <p>This is the main reason for purchasing used imported cars. It is estimated that more than 75% of new registered cars per year are used cars (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2015d) with lower energy efficiency compared to new vehicles.</p> <p>Investments in energy efficiency improvement in the buildings sector are usually conducted by using bank loans. Availability of loan, as well as amount of money</p>

Types of barriers	Barriers in the buildings sector	Barriers in the transport sector	Description (how these barriers affect each sector)
			borrowed, are closely related to personal/household income. Currently, population borrows mainly for consumer goods, and has already used almost half of its creditworthiness for that purpose (Econoler, 2012). Available resources for investments in energy efficiency in households sector are limited.
	Lack of dedicated financing	Lack of dedicated financing	Currently, only limited dedicated funds or financial mechanisms for the public sector projects for energy efficiency improvement in the buildings sector are available. The Law on Efficient Use of Energy (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013a) has envisaged national Energy Efficiency Fund. The Fund was established in 2014, but with limited resources (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment 2014h). For the transport sector, there are no dedicated funds or financial mechanisms for supporting the projects on energy efficiency (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014c).
Institutional	Institutional Capacity of the Government of Serbia	Institutional Capacity of the Government of Serbia	Closing down of the only agency in the country, devoted to supporting energy efficiency, in 2012, can be interpreted and understood as a bad sign in the market. At national level, energy efficiency is under the authority of the Ministry in charge for energy activities – Department for energy efficiency and renewable energy. According to the National Programme for the Adoption of the EU Acquis (European Integration Office, 2014) this Department has a total of 9 employees, of whom two are engaged under the contract of temporary employment and occasional work, and three for the project that lasts until December 2015. The Road Traffic Safety Agency, the Ministry in charge of Economy, the Ministry of Transport and the Ministry of Interior, with the Ministry in charge of the energy activities – Department for energy efficiency and renewable energy should work together towards improvement of energy efficiency in transport. Therefore, a serious work in capacity building of stated institutions and their coordination in actions for energy efficiency improvement are necessary (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013c).
	Institutional	Institutional	According to The Law on Efficient Use of Energy every

Types of barriers	Barriers in the buildings sector	Barriers in the transport sector	Description (how these barriers affect each sector)
	<i>Capacity of the local self-governments</i>	<i>Capacity of the local self-governments</i>	municipality with more than 20,000 inhabitants should introduce system of energy management. Although the Law was adopted in 2013, the secondary legislation is not developed yet (Energy Community, 2015), so only few of Serbian municipalities have introduced this system and appointed persons responsible for implementation.

1.2 ASSESSMENT OF IMPACT OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

The identified barriers are assessed (Table 2) from 'High' to 'Low', with the following criteria taken into consideration:

- The number of different resources that identified the same barrier;
- The number of sub-sectors that were linked with the same barrier;
- The easiness with which the barrier can be confronted;
- The duration of the barrier;
- The number of different policy instruments that were linked with the same type of barrier.

Table 2 Assessment of cross-cutting barriers

Impact of barriers	Description of barrier
High	Lack of Dedicated Financing
	Low purchasing power of citizens/ Households Credit Capacity
	Institutional capacity of the local self-governments
	Lack of information, knowledge and experience
Medium	Inertia
	Credibility and trust/ Mistrust in new technologies
	Institutional capacity of the Government of Serbia
	Lack of awareness of the population and local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy
Low	Social group interactions and status considerations
	Heterogeneity of consumers

1.3 POLICY INSTRUMENTS ADDRESSING CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

Table 3 outlines the policy instruments that address the cross-cutting barriers identified in the previous sections.

Table 3 Cross-sectoral barriers and relevant policy instruments

Barrier(s) in the building sector	Policy instruments addressing the buildings sector barrier(s)	Barrier(s) in the transport sector	Policy instruments addressing the transport sector barrier(s)
<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Heterogeneity of consumers</i>			
Heterogeneity of consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Labelling • Mandatory dissemination of information to energy consumers on the monthly consumption of electricity and heat, or natural gas (Horizontal measure in the second EEAP) • Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in the second EEAP) 	Heterogeneity of consumers	
<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Social group interactions and status considerations</i>			
Social group interactions and status considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Labelling • Mandatory dissemination of information to energy consumers on the monthly consumption of electricity and heat, or natural gas (Horizontal measure in the second EEAP) • Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in the second EEAP) 	Social group interactions and status considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fuel economy standards/vehicle CO₂-emission standards
<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Inertia</i>			
Inertia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Labelling • Energy management system in buildings • Mandatory dissemination of information to energy consumers on the monthly consumption of electricity and heat, or natural gas (Horizontal measure in the second EEAP) • Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in the second EEAP) 	Inertia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvements of bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure
<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Mistrust in new technologies</i>			
Mistrust in new technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Labelling • Energy audit (mandatory) - indirectly 	Credibility and trust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fuel economy standards/vehicle CO₂-emission standards

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mandatory dissemination of information to energy consumers on the monthly consumption of electricity and heat, or natural gas (Horizontal measure in the second EEAP) • Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in the second EEAP) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fuel quality standards
<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Lack of information, knowledge and experience</i>			
Lack of information, knowledge and experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education and training for energy managers • Education and training for energy efficiency in buildings • Energy management system in buildings • Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in the second EEAP) 	Lack of information, knowledge and experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in the second EEAP)
<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Lack of awareness of the population and local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy</i>			
Lack of awareness of the population and local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education and training for energy managers • Education and training for energy efficiency in buildings • Energy management system in buildings • Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in the second EEAP) 	Lack of awareness of the population and local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in the second EEAP)
<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Missing financial resources in the private sector</i>			
Households credit capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subsidy (This policy instrument is still not applicable to household sector). 	Low purchasing power of citizens	
<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Lack of dedicated financing</i>			
Lack of dedicated financing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subsidy 	Lack of dedicated financing	
<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Institutional Capacity of the Government of Serbia</i>			
Institutional Capacity of the Government of Serbia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	Institutional Capacity of the Government of Serbia	

<i>Cross-sectoral barrier: Institutional Capacity of the local self-governments</i>			
Institutional Capacity of the local self-governments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model of Energy Service Agreement for Public Buildings 	Institutional Capacity of the local self-governments	

CHAPTER 2: KEY FINDINGS

The barriers from all categories, which have different effect on end user behaviour, influence final energy demand in the buildings and transport sectors. However, some of the identified barriers are found to be common for both sectors.

Identified common social barriers are "Heterogeneity of consumers", "Social group interactions and status considerations" and "Inertia". Importance of these barriers is evaluated as 'Low', except the Inertia which is evaluated as 'Medium'. The only common cultural barrier is "Credibility and trust"/"Mistrust in new technologies". The effect of this barrier is identified as 'Medium'. An analysis of cultural and social barriers (for the case of the Republic of Serbia) through the references is very modest. Energy Labelling (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014 a-h), as dissemination and awareness and informative policy instrument, is targeting aforementioned barriers. This policy instrument is related to labelling of different home appliances, lights and luminaries, so it is targeting buildings sector, in order to provide information about average annual energy consumption. Also, Mandatory dissemination of information to energy consumers on the monthly consumption of electricity and heat, or natural gas and Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance are envisaged as horizontal measure in the second EEAP (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b). In the transport sector, there is no developed or proposed policy instrument directed to these specific barriers, although some of developed planning instruments (Improvements of bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014a), Traffic calming (Ministry of Transport, 2013) and Traffic management systems (Public Enterprise "Roads of Serbia, 2009)) indirectly should have impact to social, cultural and even educational barriers.

"Lack of information, knowledge and experience" and "Lack of awareness of the population and local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy" are educational barriers of 'High' and 'Medium' impact. Policy instruments aimed to reduce effects of these barriers, for the buildings sector, are Education and training for energy managers (Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2015a), Education and training for energy efficiency in buildings (Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2015b), and Funding for research in energy efficiency as policy instrument for research and development, as well as BAT promotion (Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, 2010). The common policy instrument for both sectors that has been envisaged in the second EEAP as horizontal measure: Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance, still it is not developed.

Both cross-cutting economic barriers "Lack of Dedicated Financing" and "Low purchasing power of citizens"/"Households Credit Capacity" have a 'High' impact to implementation of energy efficiency measures in both the buildings and transport sectors. However, the only developed policy measure dedicated to these barriers, just partly developed for the buildings sector is Subsidy (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014 i,j). The aim of this policy instrument is to support financing activities and measures directed to improve energy efficiency in buildings, but its

implementation in the previous period has been limited only to public sector. In the buildings sector these barriers are related to other economic barriers of high importance (Distorted District Heating Price and Absence of Metering, Low Electricity Prices), which are not affecting the transport sector.

"Institutional capacity of the local self-governments" is recognized as institutional barrier with 'High' impact, while the "Institutional capacity the Government of Serbia" is recognized as 'Medium' impact institutional barrier in both the buildings and transport sectors. Education and training for energy managers and Education and training for energy efficiency in buildings are capacity building and networking policy instruments directed partly to the first mentioned institutional barrier, but in the buildings sector only. Like for most of the barriers in the transport sector, for these institutional barriers, there are no developed policy instruments.

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MAPPING AND CATEGORISING OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

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ACRONYMS

BAT	Best Available Technologies
BERR	Business, Enterprise and Regulatory Reform
BPIE	Building Performance Institute Europe
CARES	Community Renewable Energy Scheme
CCL	Climate Change Levy
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CO2	Carbon Dioxide
CRC	Carbon Reduction Commitment
CT	Community Transport
DCLG	Department for Communities and Local Government
DEC	Display Energy Certificates
DECC	Department of Energy and Climate Change
DfT	Department of Transportation
DNO	Distribution Network Operator
ECO	Energy Company Obligation
EDR	Electricity Demand Reduction
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EPBD	Energy Performance of Building Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
ESME	Energy System Modelling Environment
ESOS	Energy Saving Opportunity Scheme
EV	Electric Vehicles
FITs	Feed-in Tariff
GD	Green Deal
GGC	Greening Government Commitments
HGV	Heavy Goods Vehicle
HNDU	Heat Networks Delivery Unit
ICE	Incentive on Connections Engagement
LCC	London Cycling Campaign
LPG	Liquefied Petroleum Gas
MW	Megawatts
NCR	National Charge Point Registry
OFGEM	Office of Gas and Electricity Market

OLEV	Office for Low Emissions Vehicle
ONS	Office for National Statistics
PHEV	Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles
PiCG	Plug-in Car Grant
PiP	Plugged-In Places
R&D	Research and Development
RCEF	Rural Community Energy Fund
RCEP	Research Councils Energy Programme
RHI	Renewable Heat Incentive
RO	Renewable Obligation
ROC	Renewable Obligation Certificate
SERES	Scottish Energy and Resource Efficiency Service
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
TINA	Technology Innovation Needs Assessment
TSB	Technology Strategy Board
UKERC	UK Energy Research Centre
UK-GBC	UK Green Building Council
ULEV	Ultra-Low Emissions Vehicle
UREF	Urban Community Energy Fund
VAT	Value Added Tax
VED	Vehicle Excise Duty
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report seeks to identify cross-cutting barriers to the implementation of energy efficiency across the building and transport sectors in the UK. Such barriers include social, cultural and educational barriers as well as economic and institutional barriers. The barriers with the highest impact, based on a qualitative assessment of the available literature include the undervaluing of energy efficiency by consumers, the inertia of consumers in relation to decision making, a mistrust of new technologies in consumers as well as a lack of trusted information and knowledge within consumers, installers/manufacturers of energy efficiency technologies. Furthermore, the practical limitations of certain technologies within the current UK context (due to infrastructure, underdevelopment of some technologies and, specifically in the case of the building sector, the variety and complexity of the UK's building stock) and the current high capital costs and expected length of payback are also seen as high impact cross-cutting barriers to the uptake of energy efficiency measures.

Despite this, there are several UK policy instruments that aim to target these barriers, although none target both building and transport sectors simultaneously. In addition, it appears that more policy instruments target barriers within the building sector, than the same barrier within the transport sector. It must also be noted that a number of the UK's energy efficiency policy instruments that targeted the building sector, and sought to overcome many of the cross-cutting barriers have recently been scrapped, and consultation is out on how to proceed in terms of UK national energy efficiency policy within this sector.

The material collected through these reports will be used to inform D.2.2 'Mapping and categorising of cross-cutting barriers across buildings and transport sector'. The outcome of this report will also be used to inform WP3 and WP4. The main barriers identified for each country and affecting demand in both in buildings and transport sector, will be included in the scenarios that will be developed for both sectors in participating countries and compared using the LEAP software.

CHAPTER 1: MAPPING CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS ACROSS BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

1.1 SOCIAL, CULTURAL, EDUCATIONAL, ECONOMIC AND INSTITUTIONAL CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS IN THE UK

The mapping and categorization of cross-cutting barriers across the buildings and transport sectors is undertaken to inform Task 2.2 and D.2.2. Table 1 outlines the cross-sector barriers, identified in D.2.1, and how these barriers affect both the building and transport sectors.

Table 1 Cross-cutting barriers across buildings and transport

Types of barriers	Barriers in building sector	Barriers in transport sector	Description <i>(how these barriers affect each sector)</i>
Social	<i>Inertia/habit</i>	<i>Inertia</i>	<p>This may include inertia in decision making or basing decisions on habit (NERA Economic Consulting, 2007).</p> <p><i>Building sector:</i> Research has shown that a significant barrier in consumers in relation to purchasing and installing energy efficient technologies related to the prospect of having to change one's lifestyle; and a concern that change may have detrimental outcomes; such as a sacrifice in standards of living, and social image. It is the idea that 'it isn't broken, so why fix it?', and can affect the installation of physical improvements measures to buildings (such as new heating systems, low-carbon technologies and fabric improvements) as well as switching energy tariffs. (Lorenzoni, Nicholson-Cole, & Whitmarsh, 2007; Enviro Consulting, 2008; Diaz-Rainey & Ashton, 2008)</p> <p><i>Transport sector:</i> Industry research has shown that, similarly, consumers are also resistant to change in relation to car purchasing; even if price signals are strong – on average, car buyers are prepared to endure an increase of £1,100 (€1540) in annual running costs before switching to a different fuel, smaller engine or smaller car (RAC, 2004).</p>
	<i>Undervaluing energy efficiency / Refurbishment seen as a low priority</i>	<i>Buyer attitude</i>	<p>Building sector: The lack of salience of energy efficiency affects much of the building sector; from the uptake of energy efficient fabric improvements in domestic dwellings and commercial properties, to the installation of low-carbon generation technologies. Energy efficiency improvements may not be seen as strategic for a</p>

			<p>company and therefore not prioritised. For example, outside of the energy intensive industry sectors, energy bills are only a small proportion of business costs. Research suggests that energy efficiency is undervalued relative to other investment options and not prioritised as it might otherwise be (DECC, 2012). In relation to domestic dwellings, research suggests that energy efficient refurbishments are not seen as a high priority when changes are being undertaken within a home (Ravetz, 2008). People appear to prefer amenities such as new kitchens, bathrooms, central heating, and general repairs, instead of energy efficient refurbishments since the social gains are more obvious (Bell & Lowe, 2000). Similarly, the undervaluing of energy efficiency can be seen in relation to the adoption of microgeneration technologies; research suggests that some households are generally content with their existing system and thus see the replacement of their system as a low priority since there is not enough perceived relative advantage (Balcombe et al., 2013).</p> <p><i>Transport sector:</i> The Low Carbon Vehicle Partnership study showed that when it comes to car purchasing, environmental issues have a very low priority for private and fleet consumers. This is at odds, both with the high level of concern declared by members of the public, and with the increasing importance of environmental issues within the business sector (Lane & Potter, 2007). Research suggests people tend to discount heavily (or not take into account) future cost savings from fuel economy at the time of purchasing a car, even though it would seem to be in their own interests as well as those of the environment. (King, 2009). Evidence suggests that many UK buyers discount heavily, and some do not consider, vehicle efficiency benefits at the point of purchasing a car. They are therefore less inclined to adopt efficient vehicles than the financial incentive from fuel economy savings might suggest. In addition, the majority of buyers tend to rate the environmental impact of vehicles relatively low in their purchase criteria.</p>
<p>Cultural</p>	<p><i>Mistrust of technologies and contractors</i></p>	<p><i>Hesitation to trust new technologies</i></p>	<p><i>Building sector:</i> Research suggests that, in some cases, consumers worry that high-efficiency devices (such as some washing machines and dishwashers) will not perform as well as conventional models (NERA Economic Consulting, 2007). A frequently cited barrier to installing microgeneration systems relates to a lack of confidence that the system will perform as desired. Whilst some</p>

			<p>studies suggest potential adopters are motivated to install by confidence in performance and reliability (e.g. (Caird & Roy, 2010)), many studies cite barriers such as performance uncertainties (Brook Lyndhurst Ltd., Mori., & Upstream, 2003; Caird & Roy, 2010; Ellison, 2004; Zahedi, 2011), as well as uncertainty over the reliability, or even lack, of general and technical information, and uncertainty over the potential benefits of microgeneration (Williams, 2010), as well as access to trustworthy information/advice and trustworthy builders to install (Balcombe, Rigby, & Azapagic, 2013); <i>“I’m concerned with these people who cold call me about having loft insulation and pumping the walls full of junk ... I want to feel comfortable with the contractor, know that they will do what they say they will do.”</i> (M. Pelenur & H. Cruickshank, 2012a and 2012b).</p> <p><i>Transport sector:</i> Research has shown current full EV models are considered an inferior product in relation to ‘known’ technologies, even when fuel cost savings are taken into account. They offer smaller driving ranges and longer refuelling times at a considerable price premium (Steinhilber, Wells, & Thankappan, 2013).</p>
	<i>Social norms and accepted behaviours</i>	<i>Habit and social norm of driving</i>	<p><i>Building sector:</i> Habit, social norms and accepted behaviours can affect overall energy use in buildings, and how they use energy efficient technologies, but also can affect the decisions to install and undertake energy efficiency improvements within their building/property.</p> <p><i>Transport sector:</i> Similar to the building sector, habitual behaviours and social norms can affect purchasing decisions as well as travel decisions; evidence indicates that people base their travel decisions on approximate rules of thumb (heuristics), which may be out-of-date or incorrect, and are influenced by many factors that do not fit classical economic theory, including habit (past behaviour) and social norm (peer group behaviour) (Lynn et al., 2014). As such, consumers are more susceptible to purchasing cars that fit within ‘social norms’ including those which see cars as a status symbol, and in which energy efficiency does not rate highly in relation to other priorities.</p>
Educational	<i>Lack of access to trusted information and</i>	<i>Lack of access to trusted information and</i>	<p><i>Building sector:</i> From a rational choice model of human behaviour, if households do not know their level of energy expenditure, how energy can be reduced, by how much, or at what cost, they are unlikely to consider investment in energy efficiency. However, although</p>

	<p>knowledge</p>	<p>knowledge</p>	<p>information provision is often necessary it is rarely sufficient in itself to encourage behaviour change (NERA Economic Consulting, 2007). Occupants do not understand how much energy they use and feel they have poor control over it. Notably, these studies reveal the importance and success of providing feedback that is clear, immediate and user-specific, resulting in savings of between 5% and 15% (Darby, 2006; Hargreaves, Nye, & Burgess, 2010).</p> <p><i>Transport sector:</i> Evidence shows that significant barriers to potential plug-in vehicle and EV buyers are insufficient or inaccurate information and a lack of knowledge. Research indicates non-ULEV purchasers suggests that many have little, if any, knowledge of ULEVs (Office for Low Emission Vehicles, 2013). Further research suggests those that have some knowledge tend to be confused by negative or inaccurate media information, or be hampered by concerns over the ‘unknown’ (including imagined sub-optimal performance, potential battery degradation or low residual value) (Hutchins et al., 2013). A lack of trusted and accurate information can also lead or exacerbate consumer’s concerns about vehicle reliability; again reducing the likelihood of consumers choosing more energy efficient vehicle models.</p>
	<p>Consumer confusion / lack of awareness on savings potential</p>	<p>Consumer confusion and understanding of impact of energy efficiency</p>	<p><i>Building sector:</i> Consumers, architects, engineers, builders, contractors, installers and building operators are often not aware of savings potential, or are poorly informed about performance benefits (NERA Economic Consulting, 2007). This also involves confusion about the links between environmental issues and their respective solutions and can affect consumer decisions to buy and invest in energy efficiency technologies (Lorenzoni et al., 2007). In addition, a lack of awareness in the savings potential of energy efficient technologies in architects, engineers, builders etc can result in energy efficient measures being value engineered and not prioritised highly in refurbishment and new building projects.</p> <p><i>Transport sector:</i> It is apparent that detailed knowledge of environmental impacts, cleaner technologies and cost structures associated with road transport is extremely low (Lane & Potter, 2007), which can affect consumer decisions to buy energy efficient technologies. In practice, purchase decisions suggest that consumers take a very short-term view when weighing up vehicle purchase costs. On average, consumers apply a very high discount</p>

			rate (60 per cent), which implies that they are looking to an 18-month payback period for fuel costs. Moreover, the average motorist underestimates their car running costs by around a factor of two (King, 2009).
Economic	Capital costs / payback expectations	High purchase price and long payback	<p><i>Building sector:</i> Capital costs and payback expectations can result in consumers deciding not to invest in energy efficiency technologies, from wall insulation to microgeneration, despite many energy saving measures being financially rational. In an interview survey conducted in Manchester and Cardiff regarding the barriers that affect the adoption of domestic energy efficiency measures or behaviours, cost appeared to be the primary barrier. The cost of energy efficiency measures is mentioned with almost 25% of respondents in a further study (M. Pelenur & H. Cruickshank, 2012a and 2012b) (UK-GBC, 2008). Often the time taken for the initial outlay to be recouped is a major barrier. For most households, energy bills for the home account for 3-4% of disposable income, hence they are not a major concern. In addition, householders will be mindful that they may move home in the next few years, while many businesses will not consider non-core investments that do not pay for themselves within 3-5 years. Research in the UK has shown that two constraints felt by occupants are the total capital costs of the project and the expected returns on investment (Ross, 2011).</p> <p>It is well recognised that costs are the largest barrier to microgeneration adoption (Allen, Hammond, & McManus, 2008; Claudy et al., 2010; Scarpa & Willis, 2010; Wee, Yang, Chou, & Padilan, 2012). Capital costs are too high for the majority of potential adopters and the payback times are too long to warrant the large investment. Capital costs and the perceived payback period are closely linked to a lack of knowledge and awareness in consumers in relation to the financial potential of microgeneration; as highlighted in the survey of Pelenur and Cruickshank (2012b) the significance of cost is increased as a barrier if the benefits of the energy efficiency measures are unknown, or if the benefits are perceived to be very low. Two illustrative quotes highlight this point, <i>“The thing is, if you double glaze your house and everything, it is an awful lot of money, and how many years is it going to take before you get your money back?”</i>; <i>“... Maybe cost, even though we don't know how much it [energy efficiency measures] costs.”</i> Uncertainty over lower fuel bills and payback period was also</p>

			<p>identified in research conducted by (UK-GBC, 2008).</p> <p><i>Transport sector:</i> The annual UK Office for National Statistics (ONS) survey (Department for Transport, 2015) found that purchase costs were a significant barrier to EV adoption. Even with the reduction offered by the PiCG (Plug-in Car Grant), EVs were often deemed unaffordable.(Hutchins et al., 2013). The UK lease cost for a Prius involves a significant premium over comparable conventional models the difference appears to be due to high servicing costs associated with the small network of dealers who maintain hybrids (Lane & Potter, 2007).</p>
	<p><i>Embryonic markets / uncertainty on investment</i></p>	<p><i>Lack of market and policy certainty over innovative technologies and infrastructure</i></p>	<p><i>Building sector:</i> The UK already has an energy efficiency market but it is small relative to the size of the opportunity. While there are examples of companies focused on helping domestic and non-domestic consumers improve energy efficiency, the market remains underdeveloped, especially in comparison with the United States. Such a barrier also has an impact on the expertise within the field; this constrains the development of financial products to support energy efficiency investment and leads to high transaction costs. Without a catalyst to drive development of the market, the costs around investing in energy efficiency will remain high, reducing cost-effectiveness (DECC, 2012) and can put off not only potential investors but also consumers; one of the key characteristics of the embryonic market is that there is a lack of access to trusted and appropriate information and in the absence of clear, trusted information, many individuals do not prioritise energy efficiency investments.</p> <p><i>Transport sector:</i> Research indicates it is not known which second generation technologies may become commercially viable or when the fuels produced may be available on the market (BERR, 2008), and as such can put off potential investors. Government-supported research suggests that investment will be needed in infrastructure and the UK supply chain to support the increased usage of plug-in vehicles to 2020 and beyond. For plug-in vehicles, investment in charging infrastructure may be needed so that motorists can charge their plug-in vehicles safely and conveniently across the country. (DECC, 2011). There is a limited business case for private investment in new infrastructure until there are sufficient numbers of vehicles. This is the ‘chicken and egg’ challenge faced by</p>

			<p>the ULEV industry and an area where Government intervention is required (Office for Low Emission Vehicles, 2013).</p> <p>In addition, battery costs are also a key area of concern. For instance, (Yang, 2010) recognised that the cost of batteries is the primary barrier to making plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs) and pure electric vehicles (EVs) commercially price competitive. With current battery costs, an EV equivalent of a current production vehicle could be more than double the forecourt price. This differential is too great even for early adopters (ARUP, 2008). Without pioneering companies offering loss-leader products, early entrants to the PHEV markets are likely to continue to face high-cost batteries and such markets suffer from inadequate demand (Keith, Austin, & Sue, 2013).</p>
	<p>Misaligned / lack of financial incentives</p>	<p>Limited financial incentives</p>	<p><i>Building sector:</i> Many of the financial barriers identified related to consumer price signals. If the financial incentive associated with investing in energy savings measures was sufficiently large, households, businesses and the public sector would have a higher propensity to undertake such investments. Put simply, energy costs often represent a small share of household expenditure resulting in lack of motivation for the vast majority of consumers to take meaningful action to reduce consumption levels. Furthermore, energy pricing structures do not reflect the full environmental costs of producing energy, in particular the costs associated with climate change, and hence there is a sub-optimal level of investment (BPIE, 2011).</p> <p>This applies at the level of the individual householder, businesses (large or small), social housing providers and the public sector, particularly in the aftermath of the credit crunch. Investing in energy efficiency now also offers some protection against increasing energy prices in the future. Some of the ‘access to financing’ issues have also been identified as administrative issues (BPIE, 2011).</p> <p><i>Transport sector:</i> Companies such as DHL, TNT and UPS have stated that they are very close to the tipping point of changing to all EV’s for urban logistics, as the gap in operating costs is closing with petrol and diesel vehicles. Small changes in costs of financing and incentives could tip this balance (Gazzard, 2014). Whilst the lack of financial incentives appears to be impeding investment in the infrastructure for energy efficient vehicles, research</p>

			<p>by the Office for Low Emission Vehicles (2013) highlighted the fact that there are barriers and a lack of incentives in terms of procurement of EVs through existing frameworks as well; The report states that Government Procurement Service manages the purchasing activity of central government departments and also makes its frameworks available to the wider public sector. Through these frameworks it is currently possible to buy ULEVs but they are not included in the regular competitions or e-auctions through which buyers access the most competitive rates for vehicle purchase. (Office for Low Emission Vehicles, 2013)</p> <p>There is also a lack of incentives in terms of further R&D within the energy efficient transport sector. In one study a representative from the automotive industry cited that it would be desirable to improve the general R&D investment climate in the UK, for instance in the upcoming reform of R&D tax credits. Credits are currently only attached to corporation tax profits, but not to R&D investment in the UK. In the same study, similar views were presented by other stakeholders, for example a prominent emerging concern was that Governments should ensure that the foreign-owned car makers not only place their manufacturing in the UK, but also their R&D, as this will secure a long-term future for the industry in the UK (Steinhilber et al., 2013). Ongoing research and development work is required to support the development and deployment of the emerging generation of new ultra low carbon vehicles. (DECC, 2011)</p>
<p>Institutional</p>	<p><i>Inadequate planning and implementation on network / infrastructure</i></p>	<p><i>Undeveloped cycling infrastructure / inadequate public transport; No standards for infrastructure investments / undeveloped infrastructure for recharging</i></p>	<p><i>Building sector:</i> Medium-sized energy projects between 10-50 Megawatts (MW) are currently underused, despite having social, economic and security of supply benefits as well as improving the system efficiency of the UK's national energy infrastructure by increasing the diversity of generating capacity available and reducing the energy lost in transmission or wasted as unused heat. Currently, obtaining planning permission for such projects can be costly and time-consuming, increasing the risk if the energy projects are owned by community groups and/or small co-operatives. In addition, grid connection costs and process are seen as prohibitively high and complex, especially in areas where the grid would require an upgrade (House of Commons, 2013). UK policy in relation to the implementation and planning framework for medium-to-large scale energy efficiency projects also</p>

			<p>does not fully enable investors and other key stakeholders in the implementation of these projects.</p> <p><i>Transport sector:</i> An infrastructure for servicing and maintenance is important for the continued adoption of innovative eco-products (Lane & Potter, 2007). The Low Carbon Vehicle Partnership study notes the example of a UK Government department that, after switching to using liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), returned to using conventional vehicles as a result of maintenance difficulties and lack of experienced technicians (House of Commons Transport Committee, 2004). Such legacies seriously affect the diffusion of eco-products out of an initial niche into the mass-market.</p> <p>A report by DECC (2011) suggested investment will be needed in infrastructure and the UK supply chain to support the increased usage of plug-in vehicles to 2020 and beyond. For plug-in vehicles, investment in charging infrastructure may be needed so that motorists can charge their plug-in vehicles safely and conveniently across the country (DECC, 2011). Research also suggests a lack of systems' integration between products and systems often deters or prevents adoption of low carbon products. For vehicles this particularly applies to fuelling infrastructure (Lane & Potter, 2007).</p> <p>In one study, in order to better meet user needs, respondents suggested that the infrastructure network should expand to support them in undertaking journeys that exceeded their vehicle range (Hutchins et al., 2013). In another study, private quantitative respondents who were PiP scheme members identified several barriers to the use of public charging infrastructure, such as a lack of rapid charging facilities on the strategic road network, a lack of charge points at 'destinations' (such as hotels and restaurants), incompatibility between various charge point providers, and a lack of accessible information about the location of charge points (Hutchins et al., 2013).</p> <p>In addition, research conducted by Aldred and Jungnickel (2014) in four UK cities (Bristol, Cambridge, Hackney, Hull) showed that that substantial infrastructural improvements could and should be made in all four areas (Aldred & Jungnickel, 2014) (Transport for London, 2008).</p>
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	<p>Complex / inadequate construction standards / regulatory and planning provision</p>	<p>Unclear planning frameworks, regulations and standards</p>	<p><i>Building sector:</i> Much research suggests there is a difference between the design standard and the way the building functions in practice. (Boardman, 2007); mainly due to a lack of knowledge and skills within the construction industry as well as a lack of adequate regulation surrounding the as-built performance of energy efficient measures. This can result in undermining consumer confidence in energy efficient technologies, including low-carbon generation and heating technologies. Proper monitoring and enforcement of compliance, enforcement and quality control the process through a qualified workforce should be part of any policy package to foster deep renovation. The relatively low compliance level is a significant barrier in reaching the estimated energy savings potential.(BPIE, 2011). According to (Hamza & Greenwood, 2008), Building Regulations do improve design teams’ abilities to meet energy targets, however, many within the industry express concern about uncertainties and difficulties with compliance. (Lowe & Oreszczyn, 2008) claim that little is known regarding the actual impact of updates to the Building Regulations due to a lack of monitoring following construction (Dowson et al., 2012).</p> <p>Difficulties in the planning process may slow or prevent a project once the developers have decided to proceed and would therefore pose a barrier on the supply side. Anticipation of difficulties with getting planning permission may also put off developers or end-consumers so that potential projects fail to reach even the design stage, creating a barrier to increasing demand. (Enviros Consulting, 2008)</p> <p><i>Transport sector:</i> A lack of clarity in terms of standards and regulations is a barrier to the uptake and development of a cohesive energy efficient transport sector. The standardization of technical specifications such as cables and plugs for recharging was identified widely as an important issue by industry interviewees in a research study (Steinilber et al., 2013) as currently there is a disconnect between infrastructure installers and vehicle manufacturers (Keith et al., 2013). The additional cable that is required remains a tangible barrier to adoption (Keith et al., 2013).</p> <p>Furthermore, there is no clear regulation as to where public EV charging spots may be installed. There are unclear regulations regarding parking on spaces equipped</p>
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			with a charging spot (Steinhilber et al., 2013).
	Lack of data	Lack of research in freight efficiency	<p><i>Building sector:</i> Such a barrier impacts upon the development of appropriate energy efficient technologies, which can then lead to a lack of investment as well as uptake of energy efficient technologies by consumers (households and commercial building owners). Kohler and Yang state that the establishment of long-term scenarios faces severe problems of data collection on the past behaviour of stocks (Kohler & Yang, 2007). Boardman (2007) noted that the lack of post-occupancy evaluation of recently built homes means that there are virtually no data on what level of energy consumption is being achieved in practice (Boardman, 2007). As a result, whilst it is possible that regulatory developments in the UK will mean that total CO2 emissions from new dwellings are now 40 –50% lower than the stock mean, an absence of empirical data unfortunately makes it impossible to be certain that these reductions are being achieved in practice (Lowe, 2007).</p> <p><i>Transport sector:</i> A key risk identified in the literature, is the lack of independent research and statistics on the sector that creates a knowledge vacuum which a range of interested, and often partisan parties attempt to fill. The quality of research and case studies thus provided varies enormously, and outside of peer reviewed material from reputable organisations, the content can be unreliable, and often contradictory to other material (Gazzard, 2014). This not only impacts on the type of information and knowledge given to consumers, but also can result in a lack of confidence within investors.</p>
	Difficulty of retrofitting to existing buildings	Limitations of technologies	<p><i>Building sector:</i> Due to the variety and scope in building stock in the UK, energy efficiency measures (demand and supply side) are often either very difficult to install, or are simply unsuitable for all contexts. As such, certain</p>

			<p>technologies can create extra ‘hassle’ and costs for the end-users (households and commercial building owners) which may put consumers off (Enviros Consulting, 2008). When combined with a lack of knowledge and information within both the end-users and the installers, builders and engineers etc., this can not only reduce investment in energy efficient measures but also result in inappropriate measures being installed, and reducing the potential energy savings actually achieved.</p> <p><i>Transport sector:</i> Evidence suggests that there are vehicle technology barriers, particularly in terms of increasing the volume of biofuel in road transport fuel. It is believed that most vehicles would be able to run on at least a 10% biofuel blend (by energy content) by 2020. However a study indicated that if it became apparent that a 10% (by energy content) blend would not be compatible with the vast majority of vehicles then there would be risk that the 10% energy target would not be met (BERR, 2008). Such limitations of technologies can put potential consumers off, as well as reduce investment potential.</p>
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1.2 ASSESSMENT OF IMPACT OF CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

Table 2 provides a qualitative assessment of the cross-cutting barriers in terms of their impact in energy efficiency. The identified barriers should be assessed from 'High' to 'Low', with the following criteria taken into consideration:

- The number of different resources that identified the same barrier;
- The number of sub-sectors that were linked with the same barrier;
- The easiness with which the barrier can be confronted;
- The duration of the barrier;
- The number of different policy instruments that were linked with the same type of barrier.

Table 2 Assessment of cross-cutting barriers

Impact of barriers	Description of barrier
High	Undervaluing energy efficiency (energy efficiency seen as a low priority)
	Inertia/habit
	High capital costs and payback
	Lack of market certainty
	Practical limitations of technologies
	Mistrust of new technologies
	Lack of trusted information and knowledge
Medium	Confusion and understanding/awareness of savings potential
	Inadequate planning frameworks and infrastructure
	Complex standards and regulatory provision
	Lack of data and research
Low	Social norms and accepted behaviours
	Lack of appropriate financial incentives

1.3 POLICY INSTRUMENTS ADDRESSING CROSS-CUTTING BARRIERS

The UK's overriding energy efficiency policy documents, such as the Energy Efficiency Strategy (2012) provide a comprehensive overview of policy strategy in the UK, incorporate both the building and transport sector, in terms of overcoming barriers to energy efficiency. However, in terms of policy instruments that address the cross-cutting barriers, none address the building and transport sectors simultaneously, except for energy labelling of energy efficiency technologies e.g. appliances (building) and vehicles (transport); which addresses the barriers of 'undervaluing energy efficiency' as well as a 'lack of trusted information and knowledge' and 'confusion and lack of understanding/awareness of savings potential', albeit further work is required to fully combat these barriers.

Furthermore, there is a range of sector-specific policy instrument types that seek to address these barriers including regulatory, economic, dissemination and awareness, and research and development. Table 3 outlines these policy instruments in relation to the cross-cutting barriers.

Table 3 Cross-cutting barriers and related policy instruments in the building and transport sectors

Description of cross-cutting barrier	Policy instruments in Building sector	Policy instruments in Transport sector
Undervaluing energy efficiency (energy efficiency seen as a low priority)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. the Green Deal and Energy Company Obligation, Decent Homes Standard, Zero Carbon Homes Standard, Building Regulations • <i>Dissemination and awareness/informative</i> e.g. Smart Metering implementation programme, mandatory GHG reporting scheme, Big Energy Saving Week, Energy Labelling on appliances, EPCs/DECs • <i>Economic</i> e.g. the Carbon Reduction Commitment Energy Efficiency Scheme (CRC), Green Deal Finance Company, Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI), Green Investment Bank • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. the community energy strategy and community energy efficiency outreach programme 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. EU Energy Efficiency Directive, Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS) • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Fuel Economy labels for cars • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Plug-in car and van grants, company car tax reform
Inertia in consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Greening Government Commitments (GGC) • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Carbon Trust Measures and the Smart Metering Implementation Programme • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Feed-in Tariffs (FiTs) and Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI) 	No policy instruments address this directly
High capital costs and payback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Green Deal and ECO • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Green Deal Finance Company, Warm Front Scheme, Salix Project and public sector loans, Loans to SMEs, Climate Challenge Fund (Scotland), Urban Community Energy Fund & Rural Community Energy Fund (UREF & RCEF), Community Renewable Energy Scheme (CARES) (Scotland) and Ynni'Fro (Wales), Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS), Scottish District Heating Loan Fund 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Economic</i> e.g. The Plug-in car and van grants, Plugged-In Places (PIP) programme includes the domestic chargepoint grant. Under this scheme homeowners are able to claim up to 75% (capped at £1,000 including VAT) off the total capital costs of the chargepoint and associated installation costs
Lack of market certainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. the Green Deal and Energy Company Obligation • <i>Economic</i> e.g. the CRC Energy Efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Planning</i> e.g. National Infrastructure Plan, Plugged-In Places (PIP) programme

	<p>Scheme, Climate Change Levy/Climate change Agreements, Salix Finance Limited, the UK Green Investment Bank, Re:FIT national programme, Electricity Demand Reduction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Promotion of energy services</i> e.g. publishing guidance on financing energy efficiency for the public sector • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. initiating an assessment of compatibility of energy efficiency investments with the public sector budgeting framework, innovation rollout mechanism, Technology Innovation Needs Assessments (TINAs), Green Business Awards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. UKH2Mobility project
Practical limitations of technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Updates to Building Regulations (2010 with 2012-2015 updates), Zero Carbon Homes, Code for Sustainable Homes, Decent Homes Standard, Renewable Energy Strategy, Energy Act 2011, National Planning Framework, EcoDesign Regulations and Directives • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. TSB research funding, Energy Technology Institute, National Heat Map and Strategy, Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU), Low Carbon Networks Fund, Advanced Heat Storage competition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. Research Councils Energy Programme (RCEP), Government funding for advanced biofuel research
Mistrust of new technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. National products policy (tranches 1& 2), Ecodesign regulations and Directives, quality assurance labels • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Scottish Energy and Resource Efficiency Service (SERES), Market Transformation Programme 	<p><i>No policy instruments address this directly</i></p>
Lack of trusted information and knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Smart Metering Implementation Programme • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Smart Metering and Billing, Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) and Display Energy Certificates (DECs), Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust, Open Homes Network, Energy Savings Advice Service, Committee on Climate Change Guidance • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. EU Energy Labelling Directive • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. One Stop Shop, peer-to-peer mentoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Fuel Economy labels for car

Confusion and understanding /awareness of savings potential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. EPCs and DEC's • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Smart Metering Implementation Programme 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Fuel Economy labels for car • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Vehicle Excise Duty (VED): fuel type and CO2 emission vehicle bands
Inadequate planning frameworks and infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. EU Energy Directives, Low Carbon Transition Plan, • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Carbon Reduction Commitment Energy Efficiency Scheme, UREF & RCEF, Community Renewable Energy Scheme (CARES – Scotland only) • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. Community First funding and community organisers training, peer-to-peer mentoring • <i>Promotion of energy services</i> e.g. License Lite, Time to Connect incentive for DNOs, Incentive on Connections Engagement (ICE) for DNOs • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. CHP Development Map, Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Planning</i> e.g. National Infrastructure Plan, Plugged-in Places (The Plug-In Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy), Low Carbon Emissions Zones (regional/local authority), Eco-towns: supplement to planning policy, Development of London Bicycling Network since 2000 • <i>Dissemination and awareness instruments</i> e.g. The National Charge point Registry (NCR) • <i>Financial</i> e.g. Cycle to Work Scheme (Green Transport Plan) • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Transport for London (TfL) and London Cycling Campaign (LCC) community bicycling project
Complex standards and regulatory provision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Energy Performance of Buildings Directive Recast EU Directives (EPBD), EU Energy Efficiency Directive 2012 (EED) , updates to Building Regulations (2010 with 2012-2015 updates), Zero Carbon Homes, Code for Sustainable Homes, Planning and Energy Act 2008, Low Carbon Transition Plan, Home Energy Conservation Act, Decent Homes Standard, Energy Act 2011 • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. funding for facilities/management apprenticeships, funding for energy efficiency training, Green Deal Training and Certification • <i>Promotion of energy services</i> e.g. Model Energy Performance Contracts and best practice guides, quality assurance labels • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. Low Carbon Buildings Programme, End Use Energy Demand Research Centres, TSB and Innovate UK research programmes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Planning</i> e.g. National Infrastructure Plan, Plugged-in Places (The Plug-In Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy), Low carbon emissions ones (regional/local authority)
Lack of data and research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. Energy Technology Institute (incl. Energy system modelling environment (ESME)), CHP Development Map, National Heat Map and Strategy, Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU), Technology Innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. £82 million of research and development funding has now been committed to support the new generation of ULEVs and to help build the necessary skills and knowledge base here in the UK.

	Needs Assessment, TSB Future Energy Management in Buildings Programme, Invest in Innovative Refurbishment, End Use Energy Demand Research Centres	This funding is focussed on identifying and funding emerging technologies that the UK can exploit and lead on globally. Funding for development of ultra low emissions vehicles (ULEVs) e.g. Technology Strategy Board's Low Carbon Vehicle Innovation Platform; Department for Transport has initiated a number of trials to explore the real, practical benefits of energy efficiency measures for road freight. In 2012 they started a two year trial of low carbon trucks whose CO2 emissions were at least 15% lower than those emitted by equivalent diesel vehicles, to demonstrate that new fuels are feasible and practical.
Social norms and accepted behaviours	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Economic</i> e.g. regional and community level energy efficiency schemes (Climate Challenge Fund, Low Carbon Communities Challenge, NEST) • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust, Big Energy Saving Week 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Eco-driving training included in national driving tests, local road transport codes • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Fuel Good driver training • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Congestion Charges
Lack of appropriate financial incentives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. The Green Deal and Energy Company Obligation • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Climate Change Levy/Climate change Agreements, The CRC Energy Efficiency Scheme, the Enhanced Capital Allowance scheme, the Electricity Demand Reduction project, Green Deal Finance Company, Warm Front Scheme, Salix Project and public sector loans, Loans to SMEs, Climate Challenge Fund (Scotland), Urban Community Energy Fund & Rural Community Energy Fund (UREF & RCEF) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. £82 million of research and development funding has now been committed to support the new generation of ULEVs and to help build the necessary skills and knowledge base here in the UK. This funding is focussed on identifying and funding emerging technologies that the UK can exploit and lead on globally. Funding for development of ultra low emissions vehicles (ULEVs) e.g. Technology Strategy Board's Low Carbon Vehicle Innovation Platform • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Plug-in car and van grants

CHAPTER 2: KEY FINDINGS

Identifying specific barriers that affected both the transport and building sectors was difficult, in part due to some of the barriers identified in the literature review in the UK's National Report D.2.1 were very specific; such as 'unwillingness to replace heating system', and 'biofuel vehicle limitations'. Instead, 'clusters' of barriers that were similar in content and effect were identified and classified as cross-cutting barriers. A further reason why some barriers, although similar, were sector-specific is that the two sectors have fundamental differences. An example of this is the influence of the individual, and the highly complex and variability of the UK's current building stock. In comparison, the transport sector is much more dependent on government- or nationally-led influences on infrastructure and mobility. In other words, there is no 'one size fits all' in the building sector due to the variety in building stock, whereas the base transport infrastructure is national, and not reliant on individual decision-making.

Despite this, there have been common social, educational and cultural barriers identified, including; undervaluing energy efficiency, inertia of consumers, mistrust of new technologies, lack of trusted information and knowledge, confusion and understanding/awareness of savings potential and social norms and accepted behaviours. Of these six identified cross-cutting barriers, four are found to have a potentially high impact on the building and transport sector; undervaluing energy efficiency, inertia of consumers, mistrust of technologies, and lack of trusted information and knowledge. In terms of policy instruments that address these barriers, none address the building and transport sectors simultaneously. However, there is a range of policy instrument types that seek to address these barriers including regulatory, economic, dissemination and awareness, and research and development.

In terms of economic cross-cutting barriers, high capital costs and payback and lack of market certainty both have a high impact in the building and transport sector. The third cross-cutting economic barrier of 'lack of appropriate financial incentives' is rated as a low impact; mainly due to the fact that, until recently, there have been several financial incentive programmes in both the building and transport sector (outlined in Table 3). However, due to recent changes in the UK Government, these have either been reduced or pulled completely. Therefore, a reassessment of the impact of this barrier is advised following further anticipated developments in the UK's energy efficiency policy.

When assessing the institutional cross-cutting barriers, all appear to be of medium impact, except 'practical limitations of technologies', which is rated as a high impact. This is mainly due to the impact this potentially has in the building sector. However, existing, and potentially future policy instruments that address and help fund research and development in this area, as well as improving skills and training within the construction industry workforce should help negate some of the impacts of this barrier.

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